

Efficient Gray Box Checking for C/C⁺⁺ Modules

Technical Report

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Abstract

In this article, the well-known black box checking approach of Peled, Vardi, and Yannakis is specialized, optimized, and extended for practical property-oriented gray box testing of C/C++ modules. All software modules whose true behavior can be expressed by symbolic finite state machines (SFSMs) can be tested according to this novel approach. In contrast to conventional finite state machines, SFSMs can operate on input and output interfaces involving conceptually infinite data types, like real and integral numbers. Safety properties, liveness properties and combinations thereof are specified using Linear Temporal Logic (LTL), and a test strategy driven by a model learning algorithm is used to automatically create an SFSM model in the background that is equivalent to the true behavior of the module under test. The model learned by testing is checked with respect to fulfillment of the desired property, using standard LTL property checking algorithms. Various new optimization strategies allow for early detection of property violations. Moreover, the application of fuzz testing in the first testing phase accelerates the original black box checking approach in a considerable way, at the same time avoiding infeasible checks due to memory exhaustion. This combined testing and model checking approach is complete in the sense that passing the suite proves that the module under test satisfies the specified property, provided that certain hypotheses about the size of the module's state space and the conditions and assignment expressions used in the code are fulfilled. Since these hypotheses can be easily checked by static code analyses, the gray box checking approach presented here is a viable alternative to "conventional" software model checking. All test and model checking algorithms presented here have been implemented in open source libraries and can be directly applied on a server farm in the cloud with an open interface provided by the authors' research group.

KEYWORDS

Property-oriented testing, Module testing, Linear Temporal Logic, Model learning, Black box checking, Gray box checking, Formal verification

1 | INTRODUCTION

1.1 | Objectives

In this article, we apply the concept of *black box checking*, as originally presented by Peled et al. [29, 30], in the context of gray box software module testing. Given an LTL property φ , tests are executed for learning the true behavior of an implementation under test (IuT) which is a software module \mathcal{S} ; this behavior is expressed by means of an initially unknown symbolic finite state machine \mathcal{M} . While trying to learn the true representation of \mathcal{M} from the test cases executed so far, violations of φ are detected either by means of a monitor checking the reactions of \mathcal{S} to the test case inputs, or during model checking the model increments $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{M}_1, \mathcal{M}_2, \dots$ learned so far. If a complete test of \mathcal{S} against $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{M}_k$ proves the language equivalence between \mathcal{S} and \mathcal{M} , the verification campaign terminates: \mathcal{S} fulfills φ if and only if \mathcal{M} fulfills this property. This "proof by testing and property checking" holds under certain hypotheses about the maximal number n of distinguishable states in \mathcal{S} , and the guard expressions

and output assignments used by \mathcal{S} . This information can be extracted from the IuT by means of static analyses. Since these analyses are fairly simple and do not require the full understanding of the programming language semantics, this approach to property verification is a suitable method for testing modules programmed using complex programming languages like C++, Java, C#, where software model checkers accepting the complete syntax do not exist.

The approach described in this article is particularly useful for testing *stateful* control software, where the behavior of the IuT not only depends on the actual input, but on the sequence of calls to the software module and the associated input data. Even if the internal module state can be changed by the testing environment, it would still be very cumbersome to specify the required behavior by preconditions and postconditions only, and to use separate test cases, each calling just one module function once, for the check of each transition to be verified in the IuT. With the gray box checking method advocated here, expected behavior is specified in LTL and refers to the required behavior over *sequences* of module calls, each call with different inputs.

1.2 | Background: Black Box Checking

In the original work by Peled et al. [29, 30], the model B to be learned was a *finite state machine (FSM)* in the variant of a Mealy machine operating on a finite input alphabet and a finite output alphabet. Model learning was performed using Angluin’s L^* algorithm [1]: under the assumption that \mathcal{S} has at most m distinguishable states, the black box B can be reconstructed incrementally by executing finitely many tests against \mathcal{S} . The implicit assumption of this approach is that the true behavior of module \mathcal{S} , as far as visible at its interface, can be expressed by means of an FSM. This assumption implies that \mathcal{S} must operate on a finite internal control state, receives finite-range inputs only, and produced finite-range outputs only. Here “finite” means that all input and output values can be explicitly enumerated inside the black box checker with a reasonable amount of main memory and within acceptable time.

Some tests serve to elaborate a new hypothesis about B (say, $B = M_i$), other tests serve to verify or falsify that \mathcal{S} is language-equivalent to the current version of B . For the latter task, the W-Method [10, 37] was used. This is a *complete* testing method in the sense that, under the hypothesis that \mathcal{S} has at most n states, \mathcal{S} passes the tests generated by the W-Method if and only if it is language-equivalent to M_i . Failed test cases can be used by the L^* -algorithm to modify and extend M_i , in order to create a refined model version M_{i+1} .

Using model checking, each new version of B is verified against φ . To this end, the product of B and a Büchi automaton P accepting $\neg\varphi$ is constructed. If the language of product automaton $B \times P$ is non-empty, this indicates the existence of a *counterexample*, that is, an infinite input/output sequence π violating φ [3]. For safety properties, the violation of φ can already be demonstrated on a finite prefix π' of π [34]. For liveness properties, omega regularity implies that the infinite counterexample π can be written as $\pi_1\pi_2^\omega$ (infinitely many copies of π_2 are appended to π_1), with finite input/output sequences π_1, π_2 [3]. Since \mathcal{S} is assumed to have at most n states, it accepts $\pi = \pi_1\pi_2^\omega$ if and only if it accepts $\pi_1\pi_2^n$, since the latter already implies the existence of a “lasso” [6] starting with π_1 and ending in a loop over the same sequence of finitely many states, endlessly repeating π_2 . Therefore, either π' or $\pi_1\pi_2^n$ can be run as a finite test against \mathcal{S} . If the counterexample is accepted by \mathcal{S} , an error has been found, and the combined learning and testing process can be aborted. If \mathcal{S} does not accept the counterexample, this information can again be used to update B via continued learning. If the latest increment $B = M_k$ passes the check against φ , and the complete test suite proves that \mathcal{S} and B are language-equivalent, the black box checking campaign has *proven* that \mathcal{S} satisfies φ , under the hypothesis that \mathcal{S} has at most n distinguishable states.

1.3 | Contributions

Gray Box Checking for Software Module Verification

The main objective of this contribution is to provide the theoretical foundations and a software platform enabling the practical application of an extended and optimized *gray box checking* method to C/C++ module testing of sequential, terminating software functions or methods in the context of software development for embedded control systems. Our underlying theory enables this for any higher programming language, such as Java or C#, but this is currently not supported by the checking software. We use the term ‘gray box checking’, since the test preparation only requires to extract branching and loop conditions, as well as output assignments from the code, and to provide an upper bound for the number of internal control states in the module.

To “shift” the original black box checking approach towards practical applicability, we regard the following challenges to be the most important ones.

1. Get rid of the limitation that the true IuT behavior should be equivalent to a finite state machine, so that the restriction to finite input and output alphabets that can be enumerated during the learning process can be dropped.
2. Mitigate the complexity problems caused by the need to apply complete testing methods during the learning process.

We consider the first problem as crucial, because many control applications use input data from analogue sensors and produce outputs for analogue actuators, so that interface types require large integers, fixed point arithmetic, or floating point numbers that cannot be explicitly enumerated during the learning and checking process. The second problem simply prevents the checking process to terminate successfully, since it is aborted due to insufficient memory, or the overall checking time required is too long.

To tackle the first challenge, we advocate the use of *symbolic finite state machines (SFSM)* to represent the true behavior of the software modules under test. SFSMs still operate on a finite control state space, but they admit guard conditions over input variables corresponding to branching or loop conditions in the software module to be verified. Moreover, they allow assignments to output variables. The data types of input and output variables are allowed to be conceptually infinite, that is, too large to be effectively enumerated by learning and checking algorithms. As stated by the authors before [17], symbolic finite state machines offer a good compromise between semantic tractability and expressiveness. This makes SFSMs well-suited for modeling control systems with inputs obtained from discrete or analogue sensors and outputs to likewise discrete or analogue actuators, where the control decisions depend on the guard valuations for the given inputs and on a finite number of internal control states. Typical systems of this kind are airbag controllers, speed monitors [20], or train protection units for autonomous trains [13]. As described in Section 9, other authors also favor more general state machines similar to SFSMs, in order to broaden the applicability of their testing methodologies.

A closer analysis of the second challenge (see also Section 4.1.2) shows that the complexity problem described can be mitigated by performing a random search for distinguishable SFSM states prior to the proper learning process: the more distinguishable states of the SFSM to be learned are known beforehand, the smaller is the difference between the *potential number* m of distinguishable states in the true behavior and the number n of states encoded in the current model version to be tested for behavioral equivalence with the IuT. Since the number of test cases to be checked for a complete equivalence test is exponential in the difference $(m - n)$ between potential and currently assumed states, it is effective to keep this difference as small as possible. Therefore, we use *fuzz testing* [22] as an initial phase before starting the learning process, with the objective to identify as many distinguishable states of the IuT as possible. All phases of the gray box checking process make use of a *monitor* as used in runtime verification, with the objective to detect safety violations as early as possible [4]. This avoids having to learn the complete model of the IuT behavior if safety violations are found at an early state. Also, as suggested already by Peled et al. [29, 30], checks for violation of liveness properties can be made in the IuT, if preliminary model versions contain these errors, and it can be shown that the offending traces can also be executed by the IuT.

Tool Support

In this article, both the underlying theory and the available tool support are described in a comprehensive manner. The tool support consists of several open source libraries that are available to other researchers or developers for reuse and extension. Moreover, an open cloud installation of the complete tool platform is available, so that experimental software tests can be performed in the cloud for evaluation purposes, research, and non-commercial applications.

The top-level structure of the tool platform is shown in Figure 1. A *test harness* controls the fuzzing phase and the learning process and performs LTL model checking. During fuzzing and learning the harness also runs the monitor for early detection of safety violations. To abstract from concrete, IuT-specific interfaces and to cope with large input/output data types, the test harness uses *symbolic input equivalence classes* to stimulate the IuT and checks IuT responses represented as *symbolic outputs*. The associated refinement steps to produce concrete input data to the IuT and to abstract concrete outputs back to symbolic ones are performed by the *test wrapper* which also calls the concrete functions or methods of the IuT.

FIGURE 1 SFSM Tester configuration for learning and testing.

Relation to Previous Work

The article presented here is a followup publication to a previous conference paper by the same authors [9]. There, it has been demonstrated how

1. The use of SFSMs increases the applicability of the original Black Box Checking approach [30] for practical software module testing.
2. The initial application of Fuzzing helps to reduce the learning and testing complexity, both with respect to memory usage and execution time.
3. The application of the $L^\#$ algorithm [36] instead of Angluin's original L^* algorithm and the use of an incremental H-Method instead of the standard W-Method makes learning and checking of model hypotheses more effective.

New Contributions

The objectives and background descriptions in this section and a part of Section 9 on related work have been taken verbatim from the conference paper [9]. Apart from that, the presentation of the underlying theory and the results achieved has been completely revised and extended. In particular, this article presents the following novel main contributions.

1. The SFSM learning process originally presented by the authors in the conference paper [9] has been revised to simplify and optimize the learning process:
 - (a) The identification of equivalence classes has been simplified by introducing a procedure for the construction of input equivalence classes. In comparison to the more complex input/output classes used in the previous publication [9], this simplifies the application of FSM learning procedures within the proper SFSM learning process. Moreover, it makes the learning and checking process more effective, since it leads to smaller input alphabets than the ones resulting from input/output equivalence classes.
 - (b) Additionally, the learning process for SFSMs has been made more effective by making it independent of the properties to be checked: it is possible to learn one SFSM representation once and for all. This model is then refined by means of a simple procedure for each LTL property to be verified. This reduces the overall verification time significantly if very many properties containing different sets of atomic propositions need to be checked.
2. Proofs have been provided for all main results, in particular for the correctness of the SFSM learning process that is generic in the application of FSM learning procedures.
3. The handling of nondeterministic code has been significantly simplified by means of a stubbing mechanism for nondeterministic functions that delegates control of nondeterministic behavior to the testing environment.
4. Two experiments have been evaluated. The first illustrates the whole learning and checking process. The second highlights how the number of input equivalence classes and the number of internal control states affects the complexity of the learning and checking process.

1.4 | Overview

In Section 2, the software modules that can be tested according to the gray box checking method described here are characterized. The behavioral semantics of software modules is described, and module specifications in Linear Temporal Logic (LTL) are introduced. In Section 3, the abstraction of input and output interfaces with large, conceptually infinite data types by means of symbolic input and output alphabets is described. The elements of the symbolic input alphabet represent the input equivalence classes the learning and checking process can be based on. In Section 4, finite state machines, complete test suites, and symbolic finite state machines used for modeling the true behavior of software modules are introduced. We describe the generic learning process for SFSMs and give the associated proof that the learned SFSM has the same behavior as the software module in Section 5. LTL property checking on a refined version of the learned SFSM is explained in Section 6. In Section 7, the optimizations already known from the previous contribution [9] are summarized, to make this article self-contained. The available tool support is presented in Section 7. In Section 8, the evaluation of two examples is performed. Section 9 reviews related work, and Section 10 presents a conclusion.

2 | SOFTWARE MODULES

2.1 | Implementation Under Test

As *implementation under test (IuT)* we consider software modules containing terminating, sequential C functions, libraries of functions, or C++ classes with their attributes and terminating, sequential methods. Let I denote the finite set of input variable symbols to the module, such as input parameters to the function or method, global variables and class attributes. Let O denote the set of output variable symbols, such as output parameters, global variables and return values (denoted by an auxiliary names). Sets I and O are assumed to be disjoint, $I \cap O = \emptyset$, and we use abbreviation $Var = I \cup O$. Let D denote the union over all variable domains. Functions and methods may depend on internal state variables, so that the function behavior may change between invocations, since the calculated output also depends on the current state. We require that the internal state is finite, so that it can be enumerated with acceptable effort. In contrast to that, input and output variables may have conceptually infinite domains. For testing libraries of functions or methods of a class operating on a joint state space, an auxiliary *selector variable* specifying the function to be called in each test step is introduced in I . A *test case* consists of a sequence of *test steps*, where each step corresponds to one function or method invocation with an associated input data tuple.

Let E be the set of output assignments and G the set of *guard conditions* over input variables, such as branching conditions (if, switch-case) and loop conditions. Guard conditions need to be expressed in terms of input variables, constants, and function symbols using input variables and constants as arguments. Output assignments may have output variables only on the left-hand side of the assignment operator and need to cover all output variables, so that the effect of outputs can be expressed as first-order formulas of the form

$$\bigwedge_{y \in O} y = \text{expression}_y,$$

where each expression_y is an expression over optional input variables, constants, and function symbols using input variables and constants as arguments. Any operator (e.g., for arithmetic) that can be handled by the programming language and also by the underlying SMT solver (currently, we use Z3 the theorem prover/SMT solver [26]) can occur in expression_y or in a guard.

These conditions about guards and output assignments are trivially fulfilled in Example 1 below; in the general case, conditional expressions or output expressions involving inputs, outputs, and local variables can be transformed using static analysis and symbolic execution techniques. This is outside the scope of this article, but tools like the clang static analyzer[†] and the KLEE symbolic execution engine[‡] allow to at least partially automate this task.

In contrast to guards and output expressions, it is not necessary to capture branching conditions or loop conditions over internal state variables or assignments to state variables: these are automatically identified in abstracted form during the learning process. This is further illustrated in Example 1 and in the evaluation examples in Section 8.

In conventional testing, *unit tests* are distinguished as a special sub-class of the more general notion of module tests [5]. In unit testing, the smallest components that can be isolated in a software structure are tested. In C implementations, smallest

[†] <https://clang-analyzer.llvm.org>

[‡] <https://github.com/klee/klee>

components are functions, in C⁺⁺ or Java, units are represented by methods or lambda expressions. If a unit calls other units, these are replaced by *function stubs* whose behavior can be determined by the testing environment. In a general module test, the sub-functions could run with their original code. This distinction applies to gray box checking as well, and both variants are supported by our tool set. We use the term *gray box module checking* when the whole module with its sub-functions are verified, and *gray box unit checking*, if only one function or method is verified, and sub-functions are replaced by stubs.

For module checking with original code for sub-functions, the guards and output assignments used there need to be extracted as well and added to G and E , respectively. For unit testing, auxiliary input variables used by the testing environment for controlling the stub behavior are introduced. This is illustrated in the next example. Both in module testing and unit testing, it is mandatory to stub nondeterministic sub-functions used anywhere in the code and to introduce the respective auxiliary inputs. This enables the test harness and the test wrapper to control the outcome of nondeterministic sub-function calls during the learning phase.

Example 1. Consider the C function `Brake()` displayed in Listing 1. It is a fictitious example of an automated braking function that could be applied, for example, in an autonomous vehicle. As input parameter, `Brake()` gets the actual vehicle speed in `float` format, with possible range $x \in [0, 400]$. As output, the function calculates the required brake force y (pointer type `float*`) to be applied on the vehicle.

```

1 extern bool brakeOnVmax(void);
2 extern float calcBrakeForceVmax(void);
3 const float c = 100.0, vmax = 200.0, delta = 10.0;
4 typedef enum {s0, s1, s2} state_t;
5
6 void Brake(float x, float* y) {
7
8     static state_t s = s0; // Internal state of function Brake()
9
10    switch (s) {
11        case s0 : if ( x < vmax ) { *y = 0; s = s0; }
12                  else if ( x > vmax ) { *y = x/c; s = s2; }
13                  else if ( brakeOnVmax() ) { *y = calcBrakeForceVmax(); s = s1; }
14                  else { *y = 0; s = s0; }
15                  break;
16        case s1: if ( x < vmax ) { *y = 0; s = s0; }
17                  else if ( x > vmax ) { *y = x/c; s = s2; }
18                  else { *y = calcBrakeForceVmax(); s = s1; }
19                  break;
20        case s2: if ( x < vmax - delta ) { *y = 0; s = s0; }
21                  else { *y = x/c; s = s2; }
22                  break;
23    }
24 }
```

Listing 1 C code of a braking function.

The actual vehicle speed should not exceed $v_{\max} = 200$ [km/h]. As long as $x < v_{\max}$, the function does not interfere with the brakes: the brake force output[§] $y \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is set to 0 (line 11) in control state s_0 . If the speed x exceeds v_{\max} (line 12), the brake force is set to (for the representation of expressions we drop the asterisk used for de-referencing C pointers)

$$y = \frac{x}{100},$$

and the function transits to control state s_2 . Since it is assumed that x cannot exceed 400, output y remains in range $[0, 4]$. In control state s_2 , braking is applied with a force that is proportional to the actual speed x (line 21, until the speed is below the threshold $(v_{\max} - \text{delta})$ (line 20). Then the brake force to be applied is reset to zero, and the function returns to control state s_0 .

When in state s_0 , special handling is applied to the case where the actual speed coincides exactly with the limit v_{\max} (lines 13, 14). The sub-function `brakeOnVmax()` is called (line 13) and returns Boolean value `true` if braking should be performed

[§] This output y is a scalar value, to be multiplied with a constant to obtain the braking force in a physical unit such as Newton.

and `false` otherwise. In the latter case, no brake force is applied, and the function remains in `s0` (line 14). In the former case, sub-function `calcBrakeForceVmax()` is called to return the actual brake force to be applied (line 13). Without specifying the detailed code of this sub-function, we assume that it always returns a value in range $[0.9, 1.1]$. This is always smaller than the brake forces to be applied in control state `s2` which are in range $[1.9, 4]$. In this case, the function transits to control state `s1`. While in this control state, the brake force to be applied is always the value returned by `calcBrakeForceVmax()`. As soon as the actual speed is again less than `vmax`, the brake force to be applied is reset to zero, and the function returns to control state `s0`. Alternatively, if the `vmax` is exceeded while in `s1`, the function also transits to `s2`, as described above for control state `s0`.

For a unit test, we do not need the original code of sub-functions `brakeOnVmax()` and `calcBrakeForceVmax()`. Instead, they are introduced as function stubs in the testing environment. To control the Boolean return value of `brakeOnVmax()` from the environment, an auxiliary Boolean input variable `xaux1` that can be set to `true` or `false` is introduced. To control the return value of `calcBrakeForceVmax()`, auxiliary floating point input `xaux2` with range $[0.9, 1.1]$ is created. A stub-file is provided as shown in Listing 2.

```

1 // globals to be set by the test wrapper as
2 // auxiliary inputs
3 bool xaux1;
4 float xaux2;
5
6 // Function stub for brakeOnVmax()
7 bool brakeOnVmax(void) {
8     return xaux1;
9 }
10 // Function stub for calcBrakeForceVmax()
11 float calcBrakeForceVmax(void) {
12     return xaux2;
13 }

```

Listing 2 Stub file for the sub-functions of `Brake` shown in Listing 1.

Summarizing, the function `Brake()`, when verified by means of gray box unit checking, induces input variables $I = \{x, xaux1, xaux2\}$ and output variables $O = \{y\}$. The variable domain is $D = \text{float} \cup \text{bool}$. The precondition restricting admissible input values is

$$pre \equiv x \in [0, 400] \wedge xaux2 \in [0.9, 1.1].$$

The set of output expressions resulting from assignments in `Brake()` is

$$E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\} = \{y = 0, y = x/100, y = xaux2\}, \quad (1)$$

the last output expression e_3 results from the stub replacements for `calcBrakeForceVmax()` in lines 13 and 18. The guard conditions extracted from the code are

$$G = \{g_1, g_2, g_3, g_4\} = \{x < vmax, x > vmax, x < vmax - delta, xaux1\}, \quad (2)$$

the last guard g_4 is induced by the stub replacement of `brakeOnVmax()` by auxiliary input `xaux1`. \square

Note that the switch-case structure over the internal control state `s` needs no to be captured for G , since it does not involve input variables. We only need an estimate for the maximal number of reachable distinguishable control states. This is trivial in this example, since `s` has an enumeration type with three values, so $m = 3$. In a more complex software module, where it might be difficult to determine whether the control states are really distinguishable, it suffices to give an upper bound. It is helpful to know that for deterministic modules, the number of of *distinguishable* states is always less or equal to the number of *reachable* states.

2.2 | Behavioral Semantics

The behavioral semantics of a software module \mathcal{S} is the set of input/output sequences that can be observed when exercising sequences of module invocations with different input values.

To formalize this notion, we first introduce valuation functions. A *valuation function* $\sigma : X \rightarrow D$ with $X \in \{I, O, Var\}$ assigns values to variable symbols. In case $X = I$, values are only defined for input variables, in case $X = O$ only for output symbols; for $X = Var$, all variables are mapped to concrete values from their domain contained in D . The set of all valuation functions $\sigma : X \rightarrow D$ is denoted by D^X . Given $\sigma : X \rightarrow D$ and $Y \subseteq X$, the restriction of σ to the domain Y is denoted by $\sigma|_Y : Y \rightarrow D$. Given any first-order formula φ over variable symbols from X , we write $\sigma \models \varphi$ and say that σ is a *model for* φ , if and only if all variable symbols occurring free in φ are in the domain of σ and the Boolean expression $\varphi[v/\sigma(v) \mid v \in X]$ (this is the formula φ with every symbol $v \in X$ replaced by its valuation $\sigma(v)$) evaluates to `true`.

A *trace* of \mathcal{S} is an infinite sequence $\kappa = \sigma_1.\sigma_2.\sigma_3 \dots \in (D^{Var})^\omega$ of valuation functions $\sigma_i : Var \rightarrow D$, such that the sequence of module invocations with input valuations $(\sigma_1|_I).(\sigma_2|_I).(\sigma_3|_I) \dots$ results in the sequence of outputs $(\sigma_1|_O).(\sigma_2|_O).(\sigma_3|_O) \dots$. This is the *synchronous interpretation* of the module's visible input/output behavior, as discussed by van de Pol [33]: inputs and associated outputs occur simultaneously, that is, in the same test step i , where inputs $\sigma_i|_I$ are applied and, after function termination, outputs $\sigma_i|_O$ are observed. The *language* $L(\mathcal{S})$ of module \mathcal{S} is the set of its possible traces and their finite prefixes. Note that while the language of module contains infinite traces, the gray box checking strategy presented in this article only requires *finite* test cases, so that only finite prefixes of infinite traces need to be executed and observed in order to decide whether a module satisfies its specification.

In general, the accessible functions or public methods of a module \mathcal{S} depend on some preconditions on the input variable that shall always be fulfilled when calling such a function or method. If \mathcal{S} is completely robust, the precondition is simply `true`, but quite often \mathcal{S} relies on certain guarantees to be fulfilled by the software environment using \mathcal{S} : In Example 1, restricting preconditions are made for physical reasons: it is assumed that the velocity of the vehicle to be controlled is always non-negative and can never exceed than 400km/h. More complex preconditions may involve several input variables. Therefore, we use notation D_{pre}^{Var} for the set of all valuations whose restrictions to input variables meet these preconditions, and D_{pre}^I for all input valuations respecting these preconditions.

2.3 | Module Specifications

The behavioral properties to be checked for a software module are specified in *Linear Temporal Logic (LTL)* [11]. The atomic propositions occurring in a formula are quantifier-free first-order expressions over input and output variables and constants of the module. The syntax of LTL formulas φ used in this article is given by grammar

$$\varphi := \phi \mid \neg\varphi \mid \varphi \wedge \varphi \mid \mathbf{X}\varphi \mid \varphi \mathbf{U}\varphi \mid \varphi \mathbf{W}\varphi \mid \mathbf{F}\varphi \mid \mathbf{G}\varphi,$$

where $\phi \in AP$ denotes atomic propositions.

Following Baier et al. [3], the semantics of LTL formulas φ is defined over infinite sequences $\pi \in (2^{AP})^\omega$ of sets of atomic propositions (for any set X , its power set is denoted by 2^X). These sequences π are indexed over natural numbers, $\pi : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow 2^{AP}$, with start index 1. They are called *propositional traces* here, to distinguish them from other traces defined and used in this article.

TABLE 1 Inductive definition of LTL semantics over propositional traces π .

$\pi^i \models \phi$	\equiv	$\phi \in \pi(i)$
$\pi^i \models \neg\varphi$	\equiv	$\pi^i \not\models \varphi$
$\pi^i \models \varphi \wedge \varphi'$	\equiv	$\pi^i \models \varphi$ and $\pi^i \models \varphi'$
$\pi^i \models \mathbf{X}\varphi$	\equiv	$\pi^{i+1} \models \varphi$
$\pi^i \models \varphi \mathbf{U}\varphi'$	\equiv	$\exists j \geq i. (\pi^j \models \varphi' \text{ and } \forall i \leq k < j. \pi^k \models \varphi)$
$\pi \models \varphi$	\equiv	$\pi^1 \models \varphi$

In the definition of LTL semantics presented in Table 1, formula ϕ denotes an atomic proposition from AP , and φ, φ' denote arbitrary LTL formulas, π is a propositional trace, and $i \in \mathbb{N}$ is an index. Expression π^i denotes the trace suffix

$\pi(i).\pi(i+1).\pi(i+2)\dots$, and $\pi^1 = \pi$. For finite prefixes $\pi' : \{1, \dots, k\} \rightarrow \mathbf{2}^{AP}$ of propositional traces π with infinite length, we write

$$\pi' < \pi \quad \equiv \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, |\pi'|\} . \pi'(i) = \pi(i),$$

to specify that π' is a finite prefix of π . The semantics of operators not contained in Table 1 is defined by syntactic transformation to defined operators:

$$\begin{aligned} (\varphi \Rightarrow \varphi') &\equiv \neg(\varphi \wedge \neg\varphi') && (\textit{implication}) \\ \mathbf{F}\varphi &\equiv (\text{true}\mathbf{U}\varphi) && (\textit{finally } \varphi) \\ \mathbf{G}\varphi &\equiv \neg\mathbf{F}\neg\varphi && (\textit{globally } \varphi) \\ \varphi\mathbf{W}\varphi' &\equiv (\varphi\mathbf{U}\varphi') \vee \mathbf{G}\varphi && (\varphi \textit{ weak until } \varphi') \end{aligned}$$

Example 2. For the function `Brake()` introduced in Example 1, we consider two properties. In natural language they are formulated as the two requirements

R1. *As long as the value of x does not exceed threshold v_{\max} , any braking intervention will apply a force that is less or equal to 1.1.*

R2. *Whenever a brake force greater or equal than 1.9 is applied, this will also be the case in the next step, unless the actual speed is decreased below $v_{\max} - \delta$.*

In LTL, these requirements are formalized by the formulas

$$\Phi_1 \equiv (\underline{y} \leq 1.1)\mathbf{W}(x > v_{\max}), \quad (3)$$

$$\Phi_2 \equiv \mathbf{G}(\underline{y} \geq 1.9 \Rightarrow \mathbf{X}(\underline{y} \geq 1.9 \vee x < v_{\max} - 10)). \quad (4)$$

According to the definition of the weak until operator \mathbf{W} , formula Φ_1 expresses that either $(x > v_{\max})$ never occurs and $(\underline{y} \leq 1.1)$ holds globally on infinite observation traces, or $(x > v_{\max})$ finally occurs on such a trace, but then $(\underline{y} < 1.1)$ is guaranteed to hold at least on the prefix of π ending exactly *before* the $(x > v_{\max})$ -occurrence. The transformation of **R2** into Φ_2 is very simple, since the formula structure follows exactly the textual structure. \square

3 | SYMBOLIC INPUT AND OUTPUT ALPHABET

Following the black box checking approach of Peled et al. [30], our basic objective is to learn the true behavior of the module under test and representing it in a model. Then the model is checked whether the desired properties hold, using conventional LTL model checking. As models, we use symbolic finite state machines as described in Section 4.2. For learning the model, the $L^\#$ algorithm proposed by Vaandrager et al. [36] is applied. This algorithm can be used for machine learning of finite state machines (FSMs) with inputs and outputs (*Mealy machines*). Since software modules may use large data types (`float`, `double`, 64-bit integers `long long`), this concept cannot be naively applied, using all possible concrete input values as input alphabet Σ_I and all possible concrete output values as output alphabet Σ_O : the size of these alphabets would result in infeasible learning tasks.

Instead, we abstract from input/output values and learn the finitely many *control states*, *guard conditions* and *output expressions* labelling the transition arrows of the *symbolic finite state machine (SFSM)* representing the true behavior of the software module under test. This approach however, is complicated by the fact that for testing the module behavior, *concrete* input values x need to be provided by the testing environment and outputs y are observed that are concrete as well. The value pair (x, y) will generally not identify the guard and output expressions applied in the software in a unique way, since they depend on the current internal control state which must be learned as well. Moreover, different guards and output expressions may be consistent with the same value pair (x, y) . These considerations lead to the introduction of *symbolic* input and output alphabets whose elements are first-order expressions specifying control decisions and outputs without enumerating all possible values of the variable types involved.

Symbolic Output Alphabet

As the *symbolic output alphabet* of a software module consists of elements representing the set of *possible* output expressions that *could* have been applied for a given pair of concrete inputs and associated outputs. Rather than set notation, a predicate specification is used, since the possible expressions that could have been applied are always identified by our tool platform using an SMT solver. Given the set E of output assignments in module \mathcal{S} and any subset $F \subseteq E$, define formula

$$\psi_F \equiv \bigwedge_{e \in F} e \wedge \bigwedge_{e \in E \setminus F} \neg e \quad (5)$$

The symbolic output alphabet Σ_O of \mathcal{S} is now defined as the set of all formulas ψ_F possessing a model:

$$\Sigma_O = \{\psi_F \mid F \subseteq E \wedge \exists \sigma \in D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}} \cdot \sigma \models \psi_F\} \quad (6)$$

Intuitively speaking, any model $\sigma \in D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}}$ of symbolic output ψ_F associates values with input and output variables such that *any* of the assignment expressions $e \in F$ could have been responsible for the outputs $\sigma|_O$ observed, and *none* of the assignment expressions $e \in E \setminus F$ could have resulted in these outputs.

Example 3. For the function `Brake()` introduced in Example 1 with $E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3\} = \{y = 0, y = x/100, y = \text{xaux2}\}$, the following conjunctions of positive and negated output expressions specify the output alphabet $\Sigma_O = \{\psi_1, \dots, \psi_5\}$.

$$\psi_1 \equiv e_1 \wedge e_2 \wedge \neg e_3 \quad \psi_2 \equiv e_1 \wedge \neg e_2 \wedge \neg e_3 \quad \psi_3 \equiv \neg e_1 \wedge e_2 \wedge \neg e_3 \quad \psi_4 \equiv \neg e_1 \wedge e_2 \wedge e_3 \quad \psi_5 \equiv \neg e_1 \wedge \neg e_2 \wedge e_3$$

All other conjunctions built according to Formula (5) do not possess a model. Valuation

$$\sigma_1 = \{x \mapsto 0, \text{xaux1} \mapsto 0, \text{xaux2} \mapsto 0.95, y \mapsto 0\},$$

for example, is a model for ψ_1 , but obviously, $\sigma_1 \not\models \neg\psi_2$, $\sigma_1 \not\models \neg\psi_3$, $\sigma_1 \not\models \neg\psi_4$, $\sigma_1 \not\models \neg\psi_5$. \square

Lemma 1. A symbolic output alphabet Σ_O constructed according to Equation (6) induces a partition of the space $D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}}$ of all valuations respecting the preconditions. The partition elements p_F are indexed over all $F \subseteq E$ with $\psi_F \in \Sigma_O$ and defined by

$$p_F = \{\sigma \in D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}} \mid \sigma \models \psi_F\}.$$

Proof. We have to show that every $\sigma \in D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}}$ is element of some partition element p_F and that no σ is member of more than one partition element. To prove the first obligation, consider any $\sigma \in D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}}$ and define $F = \{e \in E \mid \sigma \models e\}$. Then, by construction, $\sigma \models \psi_F$, and, therefore, $\sigma \in p_F$. For the second obligation, suppose that $\sigma \in p_F$ and $\sigma \in p_{F'}$ with $F \neq F'$. Then there exists an output expression e that is contained in F but not in F' or vice versa. Consequently, ψ_F contains conjunct e and $\psi_{F'}$ contains conjunct $\neg e$ or vice versa. Since σ is assumed to be an element of both p_F and $p_{F'}$, this implies that both $\sigma \models e$ and $\sigma \models \neg e$ hold, a contradiction. \square

Symbolic Input Alphabet

As the *symbolic input alphabet* of a software module \mathcal{S} with guard conditions G , output expressions E , and type restrictions pre , we use conjunctions φ of the type restrictions and positive and negated guards that are still further refined, so that

1. φ is a *path condition* in every internal control state, that is, all concrete inputs solving φ take the same (control state-dependent) path through the software module's control flow graph, and
2. all concrete inputs solving φ can solve the same set of symbolic outputs $\psi \in \Sigma_O$, given suitable output values.

This construction recipe is specified more formally in Table 2.

TABLE 2 Construction method for input equivalence classes

1. Let pre be the invariant type restriction specified for all input variables.
2. Let G be the set of all guard conditions extracted from the module code.
3. Let Σ_O be the output alphabet specified according to Equation (6).
4. For any set $P \subseteq G$, define a new first-order formula which is a conjunction of type restrictions and formulas from P and negated formulas from $G \setminus P$:

$$\varphi_P \equiv pre \wedge \bigwedge_{g \in P} g \wedge \bigwedge_{g \in G \setminus P} \neg g. \quad (7)$$

5. Let y denote the tuple (y_1, \dots, y_k) of all output variables $y_i \in O$. For any pair of sets $P \subseteq G$ and $Q \subseteq \Sigma_O$, define

$$\varphi_{P,Q} \equiv \varphi_P \wedge \bigwedge_{\psi \in Q} (\exists y \cdot \psi) \wedge \bigwedge_{\psi \in \Sigma_O \setminus Q} \neg(\exists y \cdot \psi). \quad (8)$$

6. Define the input alphabet Σ_I as the set of all $\varphi_{P,Q}$ created according to Formula (8), such that $\varphi_{P,Q}$ has a model:

$$\Sigma_I = \{\varphi_{P,Q} \mid P \subseteq G \wedge Q \subseteq \Sigma_O \wedge \exists \sigma \in D^I \cdot \sigma \models \varphi_{P,Q}\} \quad (9)$$

Each element of Σ_I is called an *input equivalence class* of the module.

Complexity Considerations Concerning Symbolic Alphabets

Obviously, the worst-case size of the symbolic output alphabet is $|\Sigma_O| = 2^{|E|}$. In practice, the size of Σ_O is considerably smaller, since only a much smaller subset of first-order formulas ψ_F built according to Equation (5) have models. Therefore, the number of subsets $Q \subseteq \Sigma_O$ leading to feasible conjuncts of input classes $\varphi_{P,Q}$ (Formula (8)) is far smaller than $2^{2^{|E|}}$. Finally, the number of subsets $P \subseteq G$ leading to formulas φ_P (Formula (7)) possessing models will be usually much smaller than the worst-case number $2^{|G|}$.

Still, the worst case sizes $|\Sigma_O| = 2^{|E|}$ and $|\Sigma_I| = 2^{|G|} \cdot 2^{2^{|E|}}$ indicate that it is advisable to always construct Σ_I and Σ_O incrementally using, for example, suitable decision tree structures, so that it is avoided to initially enumerate all formulas that are syntactically possible.

Example 4. Consider the guard conjunction

$$c \equiv pre \wedge g_1 \wedge \neg g_2 \wedge g_3 \wedge g_4 \equiv x \in [0, 190) \wedge x_{aux1} \wedge x_{aux2} \in [0.9, 1.1].$$

While all (x, x_{aux1}, x_{aux2}) solving this conjunction will lead to the execution of the same (control state-dependent) path through the control flow graph of `Brake()`, different solutions may lead to different matching sets of output expressions. For example, any input valuation satisfying $x = 0 \wedge x_{aux1} \wedge x_{aux2} \in [0.9, 1.1]$ fulfills c and solves $\exists y \cdot \psi_1$ and $\exists y \cdot \psi_5$, where ψ_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$ is defined in Example 3. In contrast to this, all input valuations satisfying $x \in [90, 110] \wedge x_{aux1} \wedge x/100 = x_{aux2} \wedge x_{aux2} \in [0.9, 1.1]$ still satisfy c , but they solve $\exists y \cdot \psi_2$ and $\exists y \cdot \psi_4$. This induces further refinements of c . According to the general construction recipe for input equivalence classes specified in Table 2, the complete refinement of c is calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_1 &\equiv c \wedge (\exists y \cdot \psi_1) \wedge (\exists y \cdot \psi_5) \wedge \bigwedge_{i \in \{2,3,4\}} \neg(\exists y \cdot \psi_i) \\ &\equiv x = 0 \wedge x_{aux1} \wedge x_{aux2} \in [0.9, 1.1] \\ \varphi_2 &\equiv c \wedge (\exists y \cdot \psi_2) \wedge (\exists y \cdot \psi_3) \wedge (\exists y \cdot \psi_5) \wedge \bigwedge_{i \in \{1,4\}} \neg(\exists y \cdot \psi_i) \\ &\equiv x \in (0, 190) \wedge x_{aux1} \wedge x/100 \neq x_{aux2} \wedge x_{aux2} \in [0.9, 1.1] \\ \varphi_3 &\equiv c \wedge (\exists y \cdot \psi_2) \wedge (\exists y \cdot \psi_4) \wedge \bigwedge_{i \in \{2,3,5\}} \neg(\exists y \cdot \psi_i) \\ &\equiv x \in [90, 110] \wedge x_{aux1} \wedge x/100 = x_{aux2} \wedge x_{aux2} \in [0.9, 1.1] \end{aligned}$$

□

The specification of the symbolic output alphabet according to Equation (6) and the construction of input equivalence classes according to Table 2 ensure the validity of the following theorem.

Theorem 1. Given fixed sets $Var = I \cup O$ of variable symbols and type domain D , guard conditions G and output expressions E , let Σ_O be a symbolic output alphabet constructed according to Formula (6) and Σ_I a symbolic input alphabet constructed according to Table 2. Let $D_{pre}^{Var} = \{\sigma \in D^{Var} \mid \sigma|_I \models pre\}$ be the set of all input/output valuations whose restriction to input variables respect the type restrictions pre . Then relation $\sim \subseteq D_{pre}^{Var} \times D_{pre}^{Var}$ defined by

$$\sigma \sim \sigma' \equiv (\exists \varphi \in \Sigma_I, \psi \in \Sigma_O. \sigma \models \varphi \wedge \psi \wedge \sigma' \models \varphi \wedge \psi) \quad (10)$$

is an equivalence relation on D_{pre}^{Var} .

Proof. We first show that “ \sim ” introduces a partition on D_{pre}^{Var} . To this end, let $\sigma \in D_{pre}^{Var}$ be an input/output valuation. Define $F \subseteq E$ as the set of all output expressions e such that $\sigma \models e$ for all $e \in F$ and $\sigma \models \neg e$ for all $e \in E \setminus F$. Then $\sigma \models \psi_F$ as specified in Formula (5). The set F is uniquely determined, because no valuation can fulfill $\psi_F \wedge \psi_{F'}$ for $F' \neq F$, $F' \subseteq E$, since all output expressions $e \in (F \setminus F') \cup (F' \setminus F)$ occur both positive and negated in the conjunction $\psi_F \wedge \psi_{F'}$. Therefore, the output alphabet element $\psi_F \in \Sigma_O$ for which σ is a model is uniquely determined.

Let $Q \subseteq \Sigma_O$ be the maximal set of output alphabet elements ψ for which $\sigma|_I \models \exists y. \psi$ is fulfilled, such that $\sigma|_I \models \neg(\exists y. \psi)$ holds for all $\psi \in \Sigma_O \setminus Q$. Again, Q is uniquely determined since $\sigma|_I$ cannot fulfill both $\exists y. \psi$ and its negation.

Moreover, $\sigma|_I \models pre$, since all type restrictions pre are observed by all $\sigma \in D_{pre}^{Var}$. Let $P \subseteq G$ be the set of guards such that $\sigma \models g$ for all $g \in P$ and $\sigma \models \neg g$ for all $g \in G \setminus P$. This means that $\sigma|_I \models \varphi_P$ as specified in Formula (7). Again, the set P is uniquely determined. Since both P and Q are uniquely determined, there exists exactly one symbolic input $\varphi_{P,Q}$ modeled by $\sigma|_I$.

Summarizing, for every $\sigma \in D_{pre}^{Var}$ there exists a uniquely determined pair $(\varphi_{P,Q}, \psi_F) \in \Sigma_I \times \Sigma_O$, such that $\sigma \models \varphi_{P,Q} \wedge \psi_F$. This shows that “ \sim ” induces a partition on D_{pre}^{Var} .

The symmetry of relation “ \sim ” follows trivially from its defining formula (10). Relation “ \sim ” is reflexive since the partition property implies that for every $\sigma \in D_{pre}^{Var}$ a uniquely defined symbolic input φ and symbolic output ψ exist such that $\sigma \models \varphi \wedge \psi$. Setting $\sigma' = \sigma$ in the defining formula (10) implies $\sigma \sim \sigma$. Likewise, transitivity of \sim follows from the fact that these $\varphi \in \Sigma_I$ and $\psi \in \Sigma_O$ exist for any given $\sigma \in D_{pre}^{Var}$ and that they are uniquely determined by σ . This proves that “ \sim ” is an equivalence relation. \square

In the proof of Theorem 1, it has been shown that the symbolic input alphabet Σ_I also partitions the set $D_{pre}^I = \{\sigma \in D^I \mid \sigma \models pre\}$ of input valuations respecting the type restrictions. This fact will be useful in other situations, so it is stated here as a corollary.

Corollary 1. The symbolic input alphabet Σ_I induces an equivalence relation $\sim_I \subseteq D_{pre}^I \times D_{pre}^I$ on the set of input valuations respecting the preconditions by

$$\sigma \sim_I \sigma' \equiv (\exists \varphi \in \Sigma_I. \sigma \models \varphi \wedge \sigma' \models \varphi). \quad (11)$$

A further useful consequence of Theorem 1, is the fact that as an equivalence relation, \sim partitions the valuation space D_{pre}^{Var} .

Corollary 2. The equivalence relation \sim specified in Theorem 1 induces a partition on D_{pre}^{Var} . Therefore, $\sigma \models \varphi \wedge \psi$ and $\sigma \models \varphi' \wedge \psi'$ implies $\varphi = \varphi'$ and $\psi = \psi'$ for all $\sigma \in D_{pre}^{Var}$, $\varphi, \varphi' \in \Sigma_I$, and $\psi, \psi' \in \Sigma_O$.

Theorem 2. Given symbolic input/outputs alphabets Σ_I, Σ_O constructed according to Table 2 and Equation (6), any pair of symbolic input φ and output expression $e \in E$ determine the associated symbolic output $\psi_F \in \Sigma_O$ in unique way.

Proof. Consider the contrary. Then there exist two valuations $\sigma_1, \sigma_2 \in D_{pre}^{Var}$ and two symbolic outputs $\psi_F, \psi_{F'} \in \Sigma_O$, constructed according to Formula 5 with $F \neq F'$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &\models \varphi \wedge e \wedge \psi_F \\ \sigma_2 &\models \varphi \wedge e \wedge \psi_{F'} \end{aligned}$$

Then there exists another output expression $e' \in (F \setminus F') \cup (F' \setminus F)$. Without loss of generality assume that $e' \in F \setminus F'$. Then e' occurs negated in $\psi_{F'}$, so the two valuations satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &\models \varphi \wedge e \wedge \psi_F \wedge e' \\ \sigma_2 &\models \varphi \wedge e \wedge \psi_{F'} \wedge \neg e' \end{aligned}$$

Assume further that e contains a conjunct $y = \text{expression}$ and e' contains a conjunct $y = \text{expression}'$ for some output variable $y \in O$, such that $\sigma_1 \models (y = \text{expression} \wedge y = \text{expression}')$, but $\sigma_2 \models (y = \text{expression} \wedge y \neq \text{expression}')$, so that $\sigma_2 \models \neg e'$. Now expression and $\text{expression}'$ cannot be constants, since then $\text{expression} = \text{expression}'$ would either hold or not hold, independently of the input valuation. Since the expressions must also be deterministic, they must be functions of the input variables. But then the construction rule for φ in Formula 8 implies that φ contains a conjunct $\text{expression} = \text{expression}'$ to ensure $e \wedge e'$, because otherwise the $\varphi \models (\exists y. \psi_F)$ would not be fulfilled. Since any solution σ of $\varphi \wedge e$ needs to satisfy $\text{expression} = \text{expression}'$, these σ will also fulfill e' , a contradiction to the assumption of existence for σ_2 . \square

4 | STATE MACHINES

In this article, two types of state machines are used: (1) symbolic finite state machines are models for the true behavior of software modules, as visible at their interface. (2) Finite state machines are needed as abstractions of SFSMs during the model learning process.

4.1 | Finite State Machines

4.1.1 | Definition

A *Finite state machine (FSM)* is a tuple $M = (S, s_0, \Sigma_I, \Sigma_O, R)$, where finite set S is the state space and $s_0 \in S$ is the machine's initial state. Finite sets Σ_I and Σ_O are the input and output alphabet of M , respectively. The set $R \subseteq S \times \Sigma_I \times \text{Sigma}_O \times S$ is the transition relation of M . The intuitive interpretation of a transition $(s, x, y, s') \in R$ is that when in state s , input x can result in output y and lead to post state s' . Due to the deterministic nature of the software modules of interest in this article (see discussion in Section 2), only *deterministic* FSMs are used in this article. This means that outputs y and target states s' are functions of the (state,input) pair (s, x) . Moreover, since the software accepts all inputs from D_{pre}^I in every state, this function is total: every input $x \in \Sigma_I$ is accepted in every state $s \in S$. The FSM M is then called *completely specified*.

A *computation of M* is an infinite sequence of transitions starting in the initial state s_0 ,

$$\xi = (s_0, x_1, y_1, s_1).(s_1, x_2, y_2, s_2).(s_2, x_3, y_3, s_3) \cdots \in (S \times \Sigma_I \times \Sigma_O \times S)^\omega,$$

such that for all $i > 0$ the tuples (s_{i-1}, x_i, y_i, s_i) are transitions of R , and, as shown for ξ , each transition but the first starts in the post state of its predecessor.

An (infinite) trace $\tau \in (\Sigma_I \times \Sigma_O)^\omega$ of some state $s \in S$ is a projection of an infinite M -computation suffix starting in s to its input/output pairs. The *language of s* is the set $L(s)$ of its traces, including all finite trace prefixes. The language of FSM M is the language of its initial state: $L(M) = L(s_0)$. Two FSMs M, M' are called *language-equivalent* if $L(M) = L(M')$.

4.1.2 | Complete Test Suites for FSMs

Let M be an FSM model with n distinguishable states and FSM M' the true behavior of an implementation. A test suite checking M' for language equivalence to M is called *complete*, if (1) every M' that is language-equivalent to M passes the suite (this is called *soundness*), and (2) every FSM M' that is *not* language-equivalent to M and has at most $m \geq n$ states fails at least one test case of the suite (this property is called *exhaustiveness*).

The size of the test suites and the length of their test cases depend on the number n of model states and the number $m \geq n$ of hypothetical distinguishable implementation states. The first complete test suite to be published was the *W-method* [10, 37] that was also used by Peled et al. [29, 30] in their original article on black box checking. A test suite \mathcal{W} constructed according to the W-method has test cases that are input sequences constructed by concatenation of finite sub-sequences from three sets:

$$\mathcal{W} = V. \left(\bigcup_{i=0}^{m-n+1} \Sigma_I^i \right). W \quad (12)$$

In this definition, V denotes a *state cover*. This is a set containing n input sequences, including the empty sequence ε , so that each sequence $v \in V$, when applied to M , reaches one of its n distinguishable states. (The empty sequence reaches the initial state.) The set W is called a *characterization set* of M and contains sufficiently many input sequences w , so that such a $w \in W$ exists for each pair s, s' of distinguishable states with the property that w , when applied to s , results in another output sequence as when applied to s' . The middle term $(\bigcup_{i=0}^{m-n+1} \Sigma_I^i)$ in the definition of \mathcal{W} consists of all input sequences over arbitrary values of the input alphabet, starting at length zero, and ending at sequence length $(m - n + 1)$.

As test oracle, it is checked for each test case $t \in \mathcal{W}$ whether the trace resulting from application of t to M' is in the language of M . Recall that for being language-equivalent, M and M' must have the same number of distinguishable states. Intuitively speaking, the test cases from $V.W \subseteq \mathcal{W}$ suffice to check whether M' has less than n distinguishable states. If these test cases pass and M' has at most m states, the test cases from $V.(\bigcup_{i=0}^{m-n+1} \Sigma_I^i) \subseteq \mathcal{W}$ suffice to reach every state in M' and check whether for any input, M' produces the same output as M in the corresponding state. If this is the case, the input sequences from $\Sigma_I.W$ can distinguish $(n + 1)$ states. Therefore, the test cases of $V.(\bigcup_{i=0}^{m-n} \Sigma_I^i).(\Sigma_I.W) = \mathcal{W}$ can reach every state in M' and detect whether M' has at least one more distinguishable state than M . This would also lead to a failure. If, however, M' passes these tests, it also has exactly n distinguishable states, and passing \mathcal{W} also implies that each input, when applied in a state of M' leads to the target state that is language-equivalent to the corresponding state reached by M . Therefore, passing the suite \mathcal{W} proves $L(M') = L(M)$, provided that M' has at most m distinguishable states.

The number of test cases needed in a W-method suite \mathcal{W} is of the order $O(n^2 \cdot |\Sigma_I|^{m-n+1})$, so it is exponential in $(m - n + 1)$. Other complete FSM testing methods, such as the H-Method used in our tool platform (see Section 7) can guarantee completeness with considerably smaller test suites in the average case, but they have the same worst-case test suite size. Therefore, it is always desirable to keep $(m - n + 1)$ as small as possible. This can be achieved by (1) obtaining a very precise bound m for the number of distinguishable states in the IuT, and (2) by finding as many distinguishable states in the IuT *before* the first hypothetical model is checked against the true behaviour of the IuT.

It is important to note that, since the complete testing methods for language equivalence are not aware of desired properties the model should have, a safety property Φ is not necessarily fulfilled by the model if none of the test cases contained in the complete suite violate the property. The technical reason for this is that the longest test traces of a complete suite are determined by the number of distinguishable states in the model and the maximal length required for distinguishing traces. In contrast to this, the minimal length of a bad prefix uncovering a violation of Φ is determined by the structure of an LTL safety property which is unrelated to the model structure. These facts are illustrated by the following example.

Example 5. Consider the FSM M in Figure 2. To test an implementation with at most 2 states against M using the W-method requires to pass the test suite

$$\mathcal{W} = V. \left(\bigcup_{i=0}^1 \Sigma_I^i \right). W = \{b, a.b, b.b, a.a.b, a.b.b\},$$

constructed from state cover $V = \{\varepsilon, a\}$, characterization set $W = \{b\}$ and input alphabet $\Sigma_I = \{\varepsilon, a, b\}$.

Now suppose we wish to check whether M fulfills safety property

$$\Phi \equiv \left((b/0) \wedge \mathbf{X}((a/0) \wedge \mathbf{X}(b/1)) \right) \Rightarrow \mathbf{XXX}((a/1) \vee (b/1))$$

It is easy to see that $M \not\models \Phi$, since input sequence $b.a.b.a$ results in trace $(b/0).(a/0).(b/1).(a/0)$, and input sequence $b.a.b.b$ results in trace $(b/0).(a/0).(b/1).(b/0)$, so $\mathbf{XXX}((a/1) \vee (b/1))$ is never fulfilled after trace prefixes satisfying $(b/0) \wedge \mathbf{X}((a/0) \wedge \mathbf{X}(b/1))$.

The test cases from \mathcal{W} , however, do not uncover this violation of Φ , since input trace $b \in \mathcal{W}$ is too short to decide whether Φ holds or whether a bad prefix has been detected, and Φ is vacuously true on the traces resulting from input sequences $\{a.b, b.b, a.a.b, a.b.b\} \subset \mathcal{W}$: none of these four test cases satisfies the premise $(b/0) \wedge \mathbf{X}((a/0) \wedge \mathbf{X}(b/1))$ of Φ . Even if \mathcal{W} contained a trace where the premise would evaluate to true, the consequence $\mathbf{XXX}((a/1) \vee (b/1))$ would never be checked, because the maximal trace length in \mathcal{W} is 3, and the shortest bad prefix of Φ has length 4. \square

FIGURE 2 An FSM violating safety property Φ , though its W-test cases do *not* violate Φ .

4.2 | Symbolic Finite State Machines

4.2.1 | Definition

The module test approach described in this article is intended for software whose true behavior can be represented by means of *Symbolic Finite State Machines (SFSM)*. SFSMs are suitable for modeling reactive systems with a finite number of control states. Inputs are obtained from a tuple of input variables that may be of conceptually infinite data types. At each processing step, guard conditions over input variables are evaluated, depending on the current control state. Guards evaluating to `true` may trigger transitions to another control state, accompanied by changes in the likewise finite tuple of output variables. In an SFSM, these changes are specified by means of first-order expressions involving output variables. Readers should keep in mind that throughout this article, SFSM models are not intended to be manually created and used for automated model-based testing (this approach has been covered elsewhere by the authors [18, 17]). Instead, they are created automatically “in the background” by means of machine learning techniques during an automated combined learning, testing and model checking process. Therefore, we assume the existence of a software module \mathcal{S} with input variables and output variables $Var = I \cup O$ and their type domain D , input type restrictions pre , guards G , and output expressions E , as introduced in Section 2. Moreover, we assume that the symbolic output alphabet Σ_O and the symbolic input alphabet Σ_I have been constructed from G and E according to Formula (5) and Table 2, respectively. This is performed by the tool support described in Section 7. More formally, a *Symbolic Finite State Machine (SFSM)* associated with $I, O, D, pre, \Sigma_I, \Sigma_O$ is a tuple

$$\mathcal{M} = (S, s_0, R),$$

where the finite set S denotes the state space, $s_0 \in S$ is the initial state, and $R \subseteq S \times \Sigma_I \times \Sigma_O \times S$ denotes the *symbolic transition relation*.

In the context of this article, R is *total* in the sense that for every $(s, \varphi) \in S \times \Sigma_I$, there exists a symbolic output $\psi \in \Sigma_O$ and a target state $s' \in S$ such that $(s, \varphi, \psi, s') \in R$. This is because the SFSMs are created here to reflect the true behavior of software modules with finite internal state corresponding to the SFSM state space S . For a software module, every input fulfilling the type restrictions pre is allowed in every possible internal state. Therefore, valuations $\sigma \in D_{pre}^I$ fulfilling $\sigma \models \varphi$ can be used for every $\varphi \in \Sigma_I$ as input in any state. Since the symbolic input alphabet Σ_I partitions the input space of all valuations satisfying the type restrictions (Corollary 1), symbolic input φ is uniquely determined by σ . Consequently, every SFSM state must have an outgoing transition labelled by φ for *every* $\varphi \in \Sigma_I$. As stated by Theorem 1, there also exists a uniquely determined symbolic output $\psi \in \Sigma_O$ such that $\sigma \models \varphi \wedge \psi$. Consequently, for any symbolic input $\varphi \in \Sigma_I$, and every state $s \in S$, R contains a transition (s, φ, ψ, s') . If R is total, \mathcal{M} is said to be *completely specified*.

4.2.2 | Symbolic and Concrete Languages

A *symbolic (infinite) computation* of an SFSM \mathcal{M} is a sequence $\zeta = (s_0, \varphi_1, \psi_1, s_1).(s_1, \varphi_2, \psi_2, s_2) \cdots \in (S \times \Sigma_I \times \Sigma_O \times S)^\omega$, such that $(s_{i-1}, \varphi_i, \psi_i, s_i) \in R$ for all $i > 0$. Its projection $\xi = (\varphi_1, \psi_1).(\varphi_2, \psi_2) \cdots \in \Sigma^\omega$ to pairs of guard conditions and output assignments is called a *symbolic trace*. The *symbolic language* $L_s(\mathcal{M})$ of an SFSM \mathcal{M} is the set of all its symbolic traces with

all their finite prefixes. The symbolic language of a state s of \mathcal{M} is denoted by $L_s(s)$ and contains all symbolic traces and their prefixes, resulting from computation suffixes starting in s .

A *concrete (infinite) computation* of \mathcal{M} is a sequence $\zeta_c = (s_0, \sigma_1, s_1). (s_1, \sigma_2, s_2) \dots$ with valuation functions $\sigma_i \in D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}}$, such that there exists a symbolic computation ζ traversing the same sequence of states and satisfying $\sigma_i \models \varphi_i \wedge \psi_i$ for all $i > 0$. The concrete computation ζ_c is called a *witness* of ζ , this is abbreviated by $\zeta_c \models \zeta$. Again, this is a *synchronous interpretation* of the SFSM's visible input/output behavior, as discussed above in Section 2.2 above.

A *(concrete) trace* is a sequence $\kappa = \sigma_1.\sigma_2.\sigma_3 \dots \in (D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}})^\omega$ of valuation functions, such that there exists a symbolic trace $\xi = (\varphi_1, \psi_1).(\varphi_2, \psi_2).(\varphi_3, \psi_3) \dots \in L_s(\mathcal{M})$ with $\kappa \models \xi$, i.e., $\sigma_i \models \varphi_i \wedge \psi_i$, for all $i > 0$. The set of all concrete traces of \mathcal{M} and their finite prefixes is called its *(concrete) language* and denoted by $L(\mathcal{M})$. For any $\alpha = (\varphi_1, \psi_1).(\varphi_2, \psi_2) \dots \in L(\mathcal{M})$, define $\alpha|_{\Sigma_I} = \varphi_1.\varphi_2 \dots$. The concrete language of a state s of \mathcal{M} is the set $L(s)$ of all infinite valuation sequences $\kappa \in (D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}})^\omega$ that are models for symbolic traces $\xi \in L_s(s)$, including their finite prefixes.

Two states s, s' of SFSM \mathcal{M} are called *distinguishable* if there exists a finite sequence of input valuations $a = \alpha_1 \dots \alpha_k \in (D_{\text{pre}}^I)^*$ such that application of a to state s leads to a sequence of output valuations $b = \beta_1 \dots \beta_k \in (D^O)^*$ that can never occur when applying a to s' or vice versa. The SFSM \mathcal{M} is called *reduced* if its states are pairwise distinguishable.

An SFSM is *deterministic* if a sequence of input valuations already determines the sequence of associated outputs in a unique way. More formally, it is deterministic if for all pairs of concrete traces $\kappa, \kappa' \in (D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}})^\omega$ satisfying $\kappa|_I = \kappa'|_I$ it holds that $\kappa = \kappa'$. Since the SFSMs considered in this article reflect the behavior of a deterministic software module as discussed in Section 2, they are deterministic as well.

The following theorem is trivial to prove, but crucial for the remainder of this article, since it shows that the symbolic language of an SFSM already determines its concrete language.

Theorem 3. *Let $\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{M}'$ be SFSMs over Σ_I and Σ_O as constructed in Table 2 and Formula (6), respectively. Then $L_s(\mathcal{M}) = L_s(\mathcal{M}')$ if and only if $L(\mathcal{M}) = L(\mathcal{M}')$.*

Proof. Let $L_s(\mathcal{M}) = L_s(\mathcal{M}')$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa \in L(\mathcal{M}) &\Leftrightarrow (\exists \zeta \in L_s(\mathcal{M}) \bullet \kappa \models \zeta) \\ &\quad \text{Concrete traces of } \mathcal{M} \text{ are models of symbolic traces of } \mathcal{M} \\ &\Leftrightarrow (\exists \zeta \in L_s(\mathcal{M}') \bullet \kappa \models \zeta) \\ &\quad \text{By assumption of the theorem, } L_s(\mathcal{M}') = L_s(\mathcal{M}) \\ &\Leftrightarrow \kappa \in L(\mathcal{M}') \\ &\quad \text{Concrete traces of } \mathcal{M}' \text{ are models of symbolic traces of } \mathcal{M}' \end{aligned}$$

Conversely, let $L(\mathcal{M}) = L(\mathcal{M}')$. By Theorem 1, every concrete trace is associated with a uniquely determined symbolic trace, because \sim is an equivalence relation and, therefore, partitions the valuation space $D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}}$. Consequently, \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{M}' have the same symbolic traces as well. \square

Obviously, the proof of Theorem 3 carries over to the symbolic languages of \mathcal{M} 's states. This results in

Corollary 3. *Two states s, s' of SFSM \mathcal{M} have the same symbolic languages $L_s(s) = L_s(s')$, if and only if they have the same concrete languages $L(s) = L(s')$.*

5 | LEARNING SFSMS

5.1 | Finite State Machine Interface of the Test Wrapper

Lemma 2. *Suppose that the behavior of module \mathcal{S} is equivalent to that of an SFSM \mathcal{M} with variables $\text{Var} = I \cup O$, type domain D , preconditions pre , symbolic input/output alphabet Σ_I, Σ_O , and n distinguishable states. Furthermore assume that function `iut_init()` has been executed once. Then, regarding Σ_I and Σ_O as uninterpreted elements of a finite input and output alphabet, respectively, function `iut()` specified in Listing 3 implements a completely specified, deterministic finite state machine over the same alphabet and with n distinguishable states.*

Listing 3 Test wrapper pseudo code.

```

1 global
2   -- data refinement map mapping symbolic inputs  $\varphi$  to concrete input valuations  $\alpha$  satisfying  $\varphi$ 
3   refMap :  $\Sigma_I \rightarrow D_{pre}^I$ ;
4
5 function getInputVal(in  $\varphi : \Sigma_I$ ) :  $D_{pre}^I$ 
6 begin
7   return valuation  $\sigma \in D_{pre}^I$  satisfying  $\sigma \models \varphi$ ;
8 end
9
10 function valToSymOut( $\sigma : D_{pre}^{var}$ ) :  $\Sigma_O$ 
11 begin
12   return uniquely defined symbolic output  $\psi \in \Sigma_O$  such that  $\sigma \models \psi$ ;
13 end
14
15 -- Test wrapper reset function
16 procedure iut_reset()
17 begin
18   initialize IuT variables ;
19 end
20
21 -- Test wrapper initialization function
22 procedure iut_init()
23 begin
24   foreach  $\varphi \in \Sigma_I$  do refMap( $\varphi$ ) := getInputVal( $\varphi$ ); -- initialize refMap
25   iut_reset ();
26 end
27
28 -- Test Wrapper main function
29 function iut(in  $\varphi : \Sigma_I$ ) :  $\Sigma_O$ 
30 begin
31    $\alpha : D_{pre}^I$ ;
32    $\alpha :=$  refMap( $\varphi$ );
33   preset input parameters and input variables of module  $\mathcal{S}$  according to input valuation  $\alpha$ ;
34   call  $\mathcal{S}$  with preset inputs ;
35   let  $\beta : D^O$  be the output valuation resulting from call to  $\mathcal{S}$ ;
36   return valToSymOut( $\alpha \cup \beta$ ); -- return uniquely defined symbolic output for valuation  $\alpha \cup \beta \in D_{pre}^{var}$ ;
37 end

```

Proof. Function `iut()` operates on inputs $\varphi \in \Sigma_I$. Since in any internal control state of \mathcal{S} , every φ represents a path condition of the module, every φ is accepted by `iut()` in every state, so it is completely specified. Input valuation $\alpha = \text{refMap}(\varphi)$ satisfies φ by construction in procedure `iut_init()`. Applying α to \mathcal{M} in some state s triggers a uniquely determined symbolic transition $s \xrightarrow{\varphi/e} s'$ to some target state s' , accompanied by output expression e . Let β be an output valuation resulting from this transition. By Corollary 2, there exists a uniquely defined $\psi_F \in \Sigma_O$ with $e \in F$, such that $\alpha \cup \beta \models \varphi \wedge e \wedge \psi_F$. Moreover, this ψ_F is uniquely determined according to Theorem 2. Therefore, ψ_F is independent on the choice of α . This ψ_F is returned as output by function `iut()` (see Listing 3, lines 36 and 12).

Since the function `iut()` itself is stateless, its input/output behavior only depends on the input and on the internal state of module \mathcal{S} . Therefore, `iut()` with its sub-functions from \mathcal{S} has at most n distinguishable states. Since distinguishable states in \mathcal{S} always have distinguishable symbolic languages according to Corollary 3, the corresponding states in FSM `iut()` are distinguishable as well. This completes the proof. \square

5.2 | Learning the Finite State Machine `iut()`

Now we can apply any machine learning procedure (for example, the one described in Section 7) for finite state machines to obtain an FSM representation of the test wrapper function `iut()` which has FSM behavior over input/output alphabet Σ_I, Σ_O , as shown in Lemma 2. To confirm that the learned FSM M is really language-equivalent to the FSM `iut()`, a complete test suite like the ones for FSM testing described in Section 7 is derived from M . Any complete test generation method requires just the known input and output alphabets Σ_I, Σ_O and an upper bound $m \in \mathbb{N}$ for the number of distinguishable states in FSM `iut()`. This upper bound has originally been obtained from static analysis of the module code. Lemma 2 states that this is a valid upper bound for FSM `iut()` as well.

The test suite is run against $\text{iut}()$. Each test case of such a suite consists of a finite sequence $\gamma \in (\Sigma_I)^*$ of symbolic inputs that can be used in a series of calls to $\text{iut}()$. These calls result in an output sequence $\delta \in (\Sigma_O)^*$ of the same length as γ . As test oracle, FSM M is used: a test case is passed if and only if the finite input/output trace $(\gamma(1), \delta(1)).(\gamma(2), \delta(2)) \dots$ observed during the test case execution is contained in the language of M . Since the test suite generated from M is complete, $\text{iut}()$ will pass all test cases of the suite if and only if $\text{iut}()$ and M are language equivalent. Between test cases, function $\text{iut_reset}()$ is called to reset the IuT to its initial state.

5.3 | From FSM to SFSM

Having learned an FSM M that is language-equivalent to FSM $\text{iut}()$, we obtain an SFSM \mathcal{M} by adopting the transition relation of M as the symbolic transition relation of \mathcal{M} and interpreting the symbolic input/output alphabets again as first-order expressions over typed variable symbols from Var . As a result, the symbolic language $L_s(\mathcal{M})$ of SFSM \mathcal{M} is identical to the language $L(M)$ of FSM M . It remains to prove that the *concrete* language of \mathcal{M} is identical to the concrete language $L(\mathcal{S})$ of the software module \mathcal{S} .

To do this, we first observe that any test suite TS_M derived from M and executed against $\text{iut}()$ gives rise to a test suite $\text{TS}_{\mathcal{S}}$ executed against \mathcal{S} : a test case $\gamma \in \Sigma_I^*$ is transformed in $\text{iut}()$ (line 32 in Listing 3) into a concrete test case α , one test step per call to $\text{iut}()$ and results in a sequence of output valuations $\beta \in (D^O)^*$ defined by this call sequence. By construction, the concrete input/output valuation sequence $\alpha \cup \beta = \alpha(1) \cup \beta(1), \alpha(2) \cup \beta(2) \dots \in (D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}})^*$ fulfills the test oracle where a test case is passed if and only if there exists a symbolic trace $\tau \in L_s(\mathcal{M})$ of \mathcal{M} such that $\alpha \cup \beta \models \tau$: this symbolic trace is always the sequence $\tau = (\varphi_1, \psi_1).(\varphi_2, \psi_2) \dots$ resulting from the call sequence to $\text{iut}()$ with $\gamma = \varphi_1.\varphi_2 \dots$, and ψ_i created in the i^{th} call to $\text{iut}()$ in line 36 of Listing 3, where concrete valuation $\alpha(i) \cup \beta(i)$ is abstracted back to the associated symbolic output in function $\text{valToSymOut}()$. Since the concrete language of an SFSM is the set of witnesses for elements of its symbolic language, passing a test case means that the concrete valuation sequence $\alpha \cup \beta$ is an element of $L(\mathcal{M})$.

Now recall that we assume that the true behavior of module \mathcal{S} can be expressed by some (unknown) SFSM \mathcal{M}' , so that $L(\mathcal{S}) = L(\mathcal{M}')$. We wish to prove that $L(\mathcal{M}') = L(\mathcal{M})$, because, as a result of the learning process, an explicit representation of \mathcal{M} is available, so that standard property checking methods can be applied on \mathcal{M} in order to prove or disprove that the properties of interest are fulfilled by module \mathcal{S} .

Suppose that the implicitly generated test suite $\text{TS}_{\mathcal{S}}$ with pass criterion $\alpha \cup \beta \in L(\mathcal{M})$ were complete. This would show that SFSM \mathcal{M}' , and, therefore, \mathcal{S} is really language-equivalent to \mathcal{M} . Therefore, we wish to infer from the knowledge that the FSM test suite TS_M exercised on $\text{iut}()$ is complete that the concrete test suite $\text{TS}_{\mathcal{S}}$ exercised on and passed by \mathcal{S} is complete as well. Indeed, a method to infer the completeness of a test suite generated in some formalism (here: SFSM) from the known completeness of another suite in another formalism (here: FSM) has been elaborated by Huang et. al. [19, Theorem 2.1]. To apply this method, several prerequisites need to be fulfilled; these are indicated by the two commuting diagrams in Figure 3.

FIGURE 3 Commuting diagrams for proving completeness of $\text{TS}_{\mathcal{S}}$.

The diagrams are interpreted for SFSMs and FSMs with at most m distinguishable states over the same fixed input/output alphabets Σ_I, Σ_O . For SFSMs, the $\varphi \in \Sigma_I$ and $\psi \in \Sigma_O$ are interpreted as first-order predicates over variable symbols from Var . For FSMs, the elements of Σ_I, Σ_O are considered as atomic alphabet members without any further interpretation. The *model map* T maps SFSMs \mathcal{M} to FSMs $M = T(\mathcal{M})$ by preserving states and using the symbolic transition relation of \mathcal{M} as the FSM transition relation of M .

Using this model map, the left diagram of Figure 3 states that language-equivalent SFSMs over fixed alphabets Σ_I, Σ_O must be mapped by T to likewise language-equivalent FSMs. This is fulfilled because of Theorem 3: language-equivalent SFSMs over the same symbolic input/output alphabets have the same symbolic language, and the latter defines the language of the FSMs associated with the SFSMs by T .

The second diagram of Figure 3 introduces a *test case map* T^* . An FSM test case consists of a finite sequence $\gamma \in \Sigma_I^*$. For our application in this article, $T^*(\gamma)$ is the sequence α of concrete input valuations created in `inut()` (line 32 in Listing 3) by means of `refMap(\gamma(i))` when being called for each element of $\gamma = \gamma(1).\gamma(2)\dots$. The *pass relation* pass_{FSM} lets an FSM M' pass a test case γ if and only if the output sequence $\delta \in \Sigma_O^*$ generated by M' in response to input sequence γ results in a finite trace $(\gamma(1), \delta(1)).(\gamma(2), \delta(2))\dots$ that is contained in the language of oracle FSM M that was the result of the learning process.

Test cases for SFSMs are sequences $\alpha \in (D_{\text{pre}}^I)^*$ of concrete input valuations. Pass relation $\text{pass}_{\text{SFSM}}$ lets an SFSM \mathcal{M}' pass test case α , if application of α to \mathcal{M}' results in a sequence of output valuations $\beta \in (D^O)^*$ such that the concrete finite trace $(\alpha(1), \beta(1)).(\alpha(2), \beta(2))\dots \in (D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}})^*$ is contained in the language of \mathcal{M} , the SFSM derived from M after the learning process.

Model map T maps any SFSM \mathcal{M}'' over the same symbolic alphabets as used by \mathcal{M} to an FSM $M'' = T(\mathcal{M}'')$ satisfying $L(M'') = L_s(\mathcal{M}'')$. Therefore, $T(\mathcal{M}'')$ passes FSM test case γ if and only if the resulting output sequence δ when applying γ to $T(\mathcal{M}'')$ results in a finite trace $\tau = (\gamma(1), \delta(1)).(\gamma(2), \delta(2))\dots$ that is contained in the language of oracle FSM M , and, equivalently, is a symbolic trace of \mathcal{M} . Moreover, the test case map ensures that $L(M'') = L_s(\mathcal{M}'')$, so $\tau \in L_s(\mathcal{M}'')$.

Suppose now that $M'' = T(\mathcal{M}'')$ passes test case γ . Since the trace τ resulting from application of γ to M'' is also a symbolic trace of \mathcal{M}'' , Theorem 2 implies that any input valuation α satisfying $\alpha \models \gamma$, when applied to \mathcal{M}'' , will result in an output sequence β , such that the resulting concrete trace $\kappa = (\alpha(1), \beta(1)).(\alpha(2), \beta(2))\dots$ is a witness of τ , that is, $\kappa \models \tau$. Since τ is also in the symbolic language of the oracle \mathcal{M} , concrete trace κ is an element of $L(\mathcal{M})$. Therefore, \mathcal{M}'' passes test case $T^*(\gamma)$.

Summarizing, the commutativity of both diagrams in Figure 3 has been established. Therefore, the prerequisites for applying the result presented by Huang et. al. [19, Theorem 2.1] are fulfilled. This result implies that if TS_{FSM} is a complete test suite for testing FSMs over alphabets Σ_I, Σ_O against oracle machine M , the test SFSM suite TS_{SFSM} resulting from translation of TS_{FSM} by means of T^* with oracle machine \mathcal{M} is likewise complete. As explained above, this test suite is exactly the one executed against \mathcal{S} in the final test for learning FSM M . Since the true behavior \mathcal{M}' of \mathcal{S} passes test suite TS_{SFSM} by construction, the suite's completeness implies the language equivalence between \mathcal{M} generated from the learned FSM M and the SFSM \mathcal{M}' reflecting the true behavior of module \mathcal{S} . This result is summarized in the following theorem that has been proven by the argument above.

Theorem 4. *The SFSM \mathcal{M} derived from the learned FSM M as described above is language-equivalent to the true behavior of software module \mathcal{S} .*

6 | SFSM REFINEMENT AND PROPERTY CHECKING

6.1 | The Need for Refinement

According to Theorem 4, the learning process described in Section 5 results in an SFSM $\mathcal{M} = (S, s_0, R)$ with n distinguishable states, over variables $Var = I \cup O$, value domain D , preconditions pre , and symbolic input/output alphabets Σ_I, Σ_O , whose behavior is language-equivalent to that of the software module \mathcal{S} . Thus, instead of *testing* \mathcal{S} with respect to fulfillment of some LTL property Φ , it is possible to apply *property checking* on SFSM \mathcal{M} , using an LTL model checking tool.

To prepare this step, it has to be ensured that all atomic propositions $\phi \in AP(\Phi)$ occurring in the LTL property Φ to be checked are visible in the symbolic traces of \mathcal{M} . This, however, is only the case if all atomic propositions are contained as a conjunct in some guard condition $g \in G$ or output expression $e \in E$ used by module \mathcal{S} . If this is not the case, the input/output alphabets of \mathcal{M} need to be refined first, in order to obtain a language-equivalent SFSM whose symbolic traces allow to be directly projected onto the atomic proposition $\phi \in AP$ fulfilled by each transition.

6.2 | SFSM Refinement

Consider the SFSM \mathcal{M} and an atomic proposition $\phi \in AP(\Phi)$. If for all $(\varphi, \psi) \in \Sigma_I \times \Sigma_O$ occurring in some symbolic transition $t = (s, \varphi, \psi, s') \in R$ of \mathcal{M} either $\varphi \wedge \psi \implies \phi$ or $\varphi \wedge \psi \implies \neg\phi$ is a tautology, there is nothing to refine, because t either implies ϕ or $\neg\phi$, regardless of the concrete valuation function $\sigma \in D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}}$ that enabled t .

If this is not the case, \mathcal{M} needs to be *refined with respect to* ψ . As an atomic proposition, ψ contains neither Boolean operators \wedge, \vee, \implies nor path operators **X, U, F, G, W**. If ϕ uses free variables over I only, a *symbolic input refinement* is performed, otherwise a *symbolic input and output refinement* is needed.

Symbolic Input Refinement

If all free variables in ϕ are input symbols from I the guard refinement is performed as follows, resulting in a new SFSM representation \mathcal{M}^ϕ .

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}^\phi &= (S, s_0, R^\phi) \text{ over input/output alphabets } \Sigma_I^\phi, \Sigma_O \\ \Sigma_I^\phi &= \{\varphi \wedge a \mid \varphi \in \Sigma_I \wedge a \in \{\phi, \neg\phi\} \wedge \exists \alpha \in D_{\text{pre}}^I \cdot \alpha \models \varphi \wedge a\} \\ R^\phi &= \{(s, \varphi \wedge a, \psi, s') \mid a \in \{\phi, \neg\phi\} \wedge (s, \varphi, \psi, s') \in R \wedge (\varphi \wedge a \in \Sigma_I^\phi)\} \end{aligned}$$

Intuitively speaking, the original transitions $t = (s, \varphi, \psi, s')$ in \mathcal{M} are replaced each by one or two transitions between the same pair of states in \mathcal{M}^ϕ , namely $(s, \varphi \wedge \phi, \psi, s')$ and/or $(s, \varphi \wedge \neg\phi, \psi, s')$, depending on whether both $\varphi \wedge \phi$ and $\varphi \wedge \neg\phi$ or only one of these conjunctions have a model. It is trivial to see that $L(\mathcal{M}^\phi) = L(\mathcal{M})$.

Symbolic Input and Output Refinement

If atomic proposition ϕ has both input and output symbols as free variables, both Σ_I and Σ_O need to be refined. This results in

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M}^\phi &= (S, s_0, R^\phi) \text{ over input/output alphabets } \Sigma_I^\phi, \Sigma_O^\phi \\ \Sigma_O^\phi &= \{\psi \wedge a \mid \psi \in \Sigma_O \wedge a \in \{\phi, \neg\phi\} \wedge \exists \sigma \in D_{\text{pre}}^{\text{Var}} \cdot \sigma \models \psi \wedge a\} \\ \Sigma_I^\phi &= \text{New set of input equivalence classes constructed according to Table 2 with symbolic output alphabet } \Sigma_O^\phi \\ R^\phi &= \{(s, \varphi', \psi \wedge a, s') \mid \varphi' \in \Sigma_I^\phi \wedge a \in \{\phi, \neg\phi\} \wedge \exists \varphi \in \Sigma_I \cdot (s, \varphi, \psi, s') \in R \wedge (\varphi' \implies \varphi) \wedge (\varphi' \implies (\exists y \cdot \psi \wedge a))\} \end{aligned}$$

A symbolic input and output refinement first creates a refined symbolic output alphabet Σ_O^ϕ by adding conjuncts ϕ and/or $\neg\phi$ to all original symbolic outputs ψ . Only the resulting conjunctions that still have a model are entered into the new output alphabet. The input equivalence classes are then re-calculated from scratch, resulting in the symbolic input alphabet Σ_I^ϕ . An original transition (s, φ, ψ, s') of \mathcal{M} is mapped to one or two transitions $(s, \varphi'_1, \psi \wedge \phi, s')$ and/or $(s, \varphi'_2, \psi \wedge \neg\phi, s')$, depending on the conditions that a new input class φ'_i $i = 1, 2$ is a refinement of the original class φ (this is expressed as $\varphi'_i \implies \varphi$) and that $\varphi_1 \implies (\exists y \cdot (\psi \wedge \phi))$ and $\varphi_2 \implies (\exists y \cdot (\psi \wedge \neg\phi))$ hold, respectively. Again, it is trivial to see that the refined SFSM \mathcal{M}' has the same concrete language as \mathcal{M} .

If the LTL property Φ to prove or disprove for \mathcal{M} contains several atomic propositions ϕ requiring refinements, the steps described above are repeated for each of these ϕ , as long as the transitions of the resulting refined SFSMs still don't imply all atomic propositions of Φ .

Note that each refinement can be mechanically calculated by creating the formulas involved an using an SMT solver supporting existential quantification to check whether the required models exist. Also note that the addition of ostensibly nondeterministic output expressions such as $y > 4$ does not violate the determinism of output assignments exploited in the proof of Theorem 2, as Σ_O^ϕ merely refines Σ_O and does not remove the deterministic output assignment expressions contained therein.

6.3 | LTL Model Checking

As a result of the refinement steps, every transition $t = (s, \varphi, \psi, s')$ in the refined machine \mathcal{M}' implies a uniquely determined (possibly empty) subset of property Φ 's atomic propositions, namely the propositions from $AP(t) = \{\phi \in AP(\Phi) \mid \varphi \wedge \psi \Rightarrow \phi\}$. Since only transitions t having a model were included in the refined SFSM, it is guaranteed that every t emanating from some state s can be triggered just by choosing an input valuation solving the symbolic input φ .

Consequently, we can map the refined SFSM \mathcal{M}' to a state machine M^Φ by preserving the states and transition arrows of \mathcal{M}' , but changing the labels of transitions t to sets of atomic propositions $AP(t)$. More formally, M^Φ is specified as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} M^\Phi &= (S, s_0, R^\Phi) \\ S &= \text{state space of refined SFSM } \mathcal{M}' \\ s_0 &= \text{initial state of } \mathcal{M}' \\ R^\Phi &= \{(s, AP(t), s') \mid t \text{ is a transition of } \mathcal{M}'\} \end{aligned}$$

With this representation, standard model checkers for LTL can be used [3]. Their basic concept is to create a Büchi automaton $\mathcal{B}(\neg\Phi)$ from the negated LTL property $\neg\Phi$. The transitions of $\mathcal{B}(\neg\Phi)$ are also labelled by sets of atomic propositions of Φ . Then the product automaton of M^Φ and $\mathcal{B}(\neg\Phi)$ is created, which treats a state as accepting if and only if its $\mathcal{B}(\neg\Phi)$ -component is accepting in $\mathcal{B}(\neg\Phi)$. If this product has an accepting trace, this implies that there exists a (possibly infinite) sequence of sets of atomic propositions violating Φ . Since M^Φ is part of the product and has been created from an SFSM that is language-equivalent to the software module \mathcal{S} , this means that \mathcal{S} violates Φ . Conversely, if the language of the product is empty since no accepting traces exist, this implies that \mathcal{S} satisfies the property.

7 | IMPLEMENTATIONS

7.1 | Learning and Checking: the Main Algorithm

We propose the gray box checking strategy specified in Listing 4 as function `gray_box_check()`. It is based on black box checking approach of Peled et al. [30], augmenting it with gray box information, the abstraction techniques described above, and fuzzing. This strategy is divided into three phases: (1) setup, (2) fuzzer-guided exploration, and (3) learning as explained below.

Phase 1: Setup In the first phase, we compute the symbolic alphabets Σ_O and Σ_I (lines 30, 31) as described in Section 3 from inputs G and E , respectively containing the guard conditions and output assignment expressions obtained from the IuT via static analysis. That is, we exploit gray box knowledge on the IuT in order to abstract from its possibly infinite input and output domains to finitely many equivalence classes. Next (line 32), we introduce a tree T that represents the prefix-closed set of all symbolic traces observed during interactions with the IuT, initially containing only the empty trace ϵ . Thereafter (line 33) the atomic propositions $AP(\Phi)$ are collected and stored in variable AP . Finally, in line 34 we construct a property monitor P for property Φ as proposed by Bauer et al. [4]. For every symbolic trace τ observed in the IuT, this monitor checks whether it is a bad prefix with respect Φ . That is, it checks whether every infinite extension $\tau.\gamma$ of τ violates the property. If this is the case, the IuT violates Φ , so that the overall algorithm can be terminated immediately, returning `FAIL`.

Phase 2: Fuzzer-Guided Exploration In the second phase, coverage-guided fuzzing is employed in order to quickly reach a large number of distinct states in the IuT and to compile a varied initial set of traces observed in the IuT, both with the aim of speeding up the subsequent learning phase. Experiments confirming the efficacy of this approach are discussed in Section 8.

Fuzzing is used for several iterations (lines 40 — 47). In each iteration, a non-empty sequence of unsigned integers \bar{b} is obtained from the fuzzer and translated into a sequence of symbolic inputs $\alpha \in \Sigma_I^*$ by mapping each integer to an element of Σ_I (lines 42, 43). Thereafter, α is applied to the IuT (line 44). All invocations of the IuT occur via calls to procedure `output_query(α)`, detailed in lines 8 — 21, which wraps around `iut()`. More precisely, every call to this procedure first resets the IuT and P to their initial states (lines 10, 11). Then, it applies each symbolic input in α in turn to the IuT (lines 14 — 18) and checks the trace observed so far via P , terminating if a violation of Φ has been observed. Finally, if α has been fully applied without any violation being detected by P , the observed trace is added to the set of observations T .

Listing 4 TODO

```

1 global
2    $P$  : property monitor;
3    $\Sigma_O$  : symbolic output alphabet;
4    $\Sigma_I$  : symbolic input alphabet;
5    $T$  :  $(\Sigma_I \times \Sigma_O)^*$ ; -- prefix-closed set of symbolic traces observed in the IuT
6
7 -- apply  $\alpha$  to the IuT and update  $T$  with the observed output, aborting if the property monitor observes a violation
8 procedure output_query(in  $\alpha$  :  $\Sigma_I^*$ ) :  $\Sigma_O^*$ 
9 begin
10   iut_reset();
11   monitor_reset();
12    $i$  := 1;
13    $\tau$  :=  $\epsilon$  -- trace observed during application of  $\alpha$ 
14   while ( $i \leq |\alpha|$ ) do
15      $\tau$  :=  $\tau \cdot (\alpha(i), \text{iut}(\alpha(i)))$ ;
16     if (monitor_step( $\tau(i)$ ) = FAIL) then abort with output FAIL;
17      $i$  :=  $i + 1$ ;
18   end;
19    $T$  :=  $T \cup \text{pref}(\tau)$ ; -- add all prefixes of  $\tau$  to  $T$ 
20   return  $\beta$ ;
21 end
22
23 function gray_box_check(in  $G$  : guard conditions;
24   in  $E$  : output assignment expressions;
25   in  $\Phi$  : LTL property to be verified;
26   in  $n$  : maximal number of states of the IuT;
27   in  $r_{max}$  : maximum number of rounds of fuzzing;
28   ) : {PASS, FAIL}
29 begin
30   -- Phase 1: Setup
31    $\Sigma_O$  := construct symbolic output alphabet from  $G$  via Formula 6
32    $\Sigma_I$  := construct symbolic input alphabet from  $\Sigma_O$  and  $E$  via Table 2
33    $T$  :=  $\{\epsilon\}$ ;
34    $AP$  := collect atomic propositions of  $\Phi$ ;
35    $P$  := property monitor for  $\Phi$ ;
36
37   -- Phase 2: Fuzzer guided exploration
38    $r$  := 0; -- number of performed fuzzing iterations
39    $\ell_T$  := 1; -- lower bound on the number of distinct states already observed
40   while (  $r < r_{max}$  and  $\ell_T < n$  )
41     begin
42        $\bar{b}$  := non-empty sequence of integers obtained from fuzzer;
43        $\alpha$  := construct a symbolic test case by mapping each element  $\bar{b}$  to an element of  $\Sigma_I$ ; -- e.g. by selecting the  $(\bar{b} \bmod |\Sigma_I| + 1)^{th}$  element of  $\Sigma_I$ 
44       outputQuery( $\alpha$ );
45        $r$  :=  $r + 1$ ;
46        $\ell_T$  :=  $|\text{maximal\_pairwise\_distinguishable\_subset}(T)|$ 
47     end
48
49   -- Phase 3: Learning using  $L^\#$ 
50    $M_1$  :=  $L^\#(\epsilon)$  -- start learning an FSM using input alphabet  $\Sigma_I$ , output alphabet  $\Sigma_O$ , the observations  $T$  already observed during fuzzing, and no counterexample
51    $i$  := 1;
52   while ( true )
53     begin
54        $X$  :=  $M_i^\Phi \times \mathcal{B}(\neg\Phi)$ ; -- Product of machine learned so far (refined for  $AP$ ) and a Büchi automaton accepting  $\neg\Phi$ 
55       if  $L(X) = \emptyset$  then begin --  $M_i$  does not violate  $\Phi$ 
56          $\ell$  := number of states of  $M_i$ ;
57         (conforms,  $\pi$ ) :=  $H(M_i, T, \ell, n)$ ; -- apply an online H-Method
58         if ( conforms ) then return PASS; -- Implementation conforms to  $M_i$ , and  $M_i$  fulfils  $\Phi$ 
59       end
60       else begin -- current model  $M_i$  violates  $\Phi$ 
61         let  $\pi_1, \pi_2$  such that  $\pi_1 \pi_2^\omega \in L(X)$ ; -- select a trace violating  $\Phi$  in  $M_i$ 
62         if ( the IuT passes test  $\pi_1 \pi_2^n$  ) then return FAIL;
63         else  $\pi$  := shortest prefix of  $\pi_1 \pi_2^\omega$  not accepted by  $S$ ;
64       end
65        $M_{i+1}$  :=  $L^\#(\pi)$ ; -- learn more elaborate model based on counterexample  $\pi$ 
66        $i$  :=  $i + 1$ ;
67     end
68 end

```

The fuzzer-guided exploration terminates as soon as one of the following conditions is satisfied: (1) Fuzzing has been performed for r_{max} iterations, where r_{max} is another input parameter of the algorithm, and the number of iterations is tracked in variable r (lines 38 and 45), or (2) the number of distinct states of the IuT observed during fuzzing has reached the upper bound n provided as input. A lower bound on the number of identified distinct states in the IuT is tracked in variable ℓ_T (lines 39 and 46), which is updated after each iteration. This is realized via function `maximal_pairwise_distinguishable_subset(T)` as follows: First, pairs of traces are identified that are distinguishable in T , where traces $\alpha, \beta \in (\Sigma_I \times \Sigma_O)^*$ are distinguishable in T if there exists $\alpha.(\phi, \psi), \beta.(\phi, \psi') \in T$ with $\psi \neq \psi'$. From these, a maximal set $S \subseteq T$ is selected such that any pair of distinct traces in S is distinguishable.[¶] Thus, no two distinct traces in S reach the same state of the IuT and hence $\ell_T := |S|$ constitutes a lower bound on the size of the IuT.

Phase 3: Learning The third phase (lines 50 — 68) finally implements learning based on the approach proposed by Peled et al. [30]. Learning is performed by repeatedly generating FSM hypotheses M_i over alphabets Σ_I, Σ_O and checking whether their refined state machine interpretations M_i^Φ correspond to the behavior of the IuT. More precisely, the learning phase begins by creating a first FSM hypothesis M_1 (line 50) using the efficient $L^\#$ algorithm proposed by Vaandrager et al. [36]. This algorithm follows the *minimally adequate teacher* framework of Angluin’s L^* algorithm [1], based on two operations: First, the set of previous observations T is extended following various rules and using `output_query()` to query the IuT. Second, after sufficient expansion of T , an FSM hypothesis is generated from T to be tested for equivalence against the IuT. In Listing 4, we represent the generation of a hypothesis as calls to $L^\#(\pi)$ (lines 50, 65) where π is either empty (i.e. ϵ) or a counterexample – that is, a trace which is exhibited either by the IuT or by the current hypothesis, but not by both.

For each generated hypothesis M_i , a series of checks is executed (lines 54 — 66). First, LTL model checking is performed as discussed in Subsection 6.3. That is, we obtain the SFSM \mathcal{M}_i corresponding to M_i and refine it with the atomic propositions of Φ , resulting in M_i^Φ . We then check using the product machine $M_i^\Phi \times \mathcal{B}(\neg\Phi)$ whether M_i^Φ exhibits a trace accepted by Büchi automaton $\mathcal{B}(\neg\Phi)$ – that is, a trace violating Φ (lines 54, 55).

If no such violation can be found, then we test whether \mathcal{M}_i is equivalent to the behavior of the IuT (line 55-59). To this purpose, we employ the complete H-Method [12] test strategy for FSM M_i . We adapted the H-Method for online testing.[#] That is, instead of computing the entire test suite and only thereafter applying it to the IuT, we interleave test case generation and application in an attempt to find failures early. This can be particularly effective if the current hypothesis contains fewer than n states, as the size of the complete test suite is dominated by factor $|\Sigma_I|^{n-|M_i|+1}$. We furthermore apply each test case to the IuT via `output_query()`, which entails applying the property monitor and updating the set of observations T . The H-Method either returns that \mathcal{M}_i is equivalent to the behavior of the IuT or returns a counterexample π that is in the language of \mathcal{M}_i but not exhibited by the IuT or vice versa. In the first case, the algorithm terminates and returns `PASS` (line 58), since the IuT conforms to an SFSM that satisfies Φ . In the second case, counterexample π is used in the generation of the next hypothesis (line 65), as the current hypothesis does not yet correspond to the IuT.

If the language of $M_i^\Phi \times \mathcal{B}(\neg\Phi)$ is not empty, then omega regularity implies that there exists a trace in \mathcal{M}_i violating Φ that can be written as $\pi_1.\pi_2^\omega$ for finite prefix π_1 and infinitely repeated finite suffix π_2 (line 61). It remains then to check whether this violation is also exhibited by the IuT. As the latter has at most n states, this can be performed by considering finite test case $\pi_1.\pi_2^n$. If the IuT does exhibit $\pi_1.\pi_2^n$ (line 62), we terminate and return `FAIL`, as a violation of Φ has been observed in the IuT. Otherwise, the shortest prefix of $\pi_1.\pi_2^n$ that is not exhibited by the IuT is used as a counterexample for learning the next FSM hypothesis (line 63 — 65).

7.2 | Tool Support: libfsmtest and libfsmtest

We have implemented the approach described above as a C++ framework depending for fuzzing tasks on `libFuzzer`[†], a coverage-guided fuzzing engine distributed as a part of the LLVM project and for the creation for LTL properties of runtime property monitors [4] and Büchi automata `ltl3tools`[‡].

[¶] Note that finding the largest such set is equivalent to finding the largest clique [7] in an undirected graph with vertices T where traces are adjacent if and only if they are distinguishable. This constitutes a computationally expensive problem, so that we currently apply a greedy heuristic.

[#] Note that the application of the H-Method constitutes another improvement on the approach proposed by Peled et al. [30], which used the W-Method [37, 10]. While both strategies exhibit the same worst case behavior in terms of test steps, the H-Method has been observed in practice to require on average significantly fewer test steps [14].

[†] <https://llvm.org/docs/LibFuzzer.html>

[‡] <https://ltl3tools.sourceforge.net/>

The framework implements Listing 4 as a *test harness* as depicted in Fig. 1, interfacing with the IuT through a *test wrapper* that implements Listing 3. Thus, only this wrapper has to be adapted to a given IuT. Sets G and E of expressions and the LTL property Φ are read from files using the `libfsmtest`[§] library, which also supports extracting the atomic propositions AP occurring in Φ , computing alphabets Σ_I and Σ_O , and making executable the property monitor obtained via `ltl3tools`. We have implemented the $L^\#$ algorithm in `libfsmtest`[¶], which also provides the data structure and related operations for FSMs.

Libraries `libfsmtest` and `libfsmtest` are available as open source software under MIT license. The entire testing strategy described here can also be performed remotely by using a cloud service, requiring no local installations.[#]

8 | EVALUATION

For the evaluation of the property testing approach described in this article, we tested the brake controller from Example 1, as well as an implementation of a fair scheduler. These modules have been fully verified by our property testing approach. Each implementation under test is implemented in C/C^{++} and consists of a single function/method serving as the main entry point of the IuT. Both the brake and scheduler implementations satisfy the general requirement that the IuT returns after processing the test inputs, so that the outputs can be observed by the test engine. Recall from Section 1 that the symbolic inputs are mapped to concrete inputs of the IuT via the test wrapper. Likewise, the observed concrete outputs of the IuT are mapped to symbolic outputs via the test wrapper. In the following subsections, the evaluation of each IuT is described in detail. The required test configuration files, as well as test wrapper implementation are sketched for each module.

8.1 | Brake Controller

In this section, the brake controller from Example 1 is tested.

8.1.1 | Test Setup

For executing tests, three resources are needed: (1) the *symbol file* providing information obtained by static analysis of the IuT to the test engine, (2) the *test wrapper* refining symbolic inputs provided by the test engine to concrete inputs to the IuT and abstracting concrete IuT outputs to symbolic outputs, as well as (3) *property files* containing the LTL property to be checked on the `Brake()` implementation. Both logical expressions contained in the symbol file and LTL formulas in the property files are specified in prefix notation, following the SMT-LIB syntax^{||}.

In the symbol file (see Listing 5), input and output symbols of the IuT are declared with the appropriate variable domains (for the `Brake()` function, the domains for both input and output variables are in $D = \text{float} \cup \text{bool}$), as listed in the symbol file section `identifiers`. Constant values like `vmax` (maximum allowed speed), `c` (divisor for the brake force calculation) and `delta` (braking threshold) are treated as configuration parameters, which are also defined as input symbols of the IuT.

The outputs to be returned by the stubbed functions `calcBrakeForceVmax()` and `brakeOnVmax()` are specified as inputs to be provided by the test engine. They are denoted by inputs `xaux1` and `xaux2`, which are simply returned by the function stub implementations.

For all input variables, `invariants` are specified in the symbol file's `invariants` section. As shown in Listing 5, the invariant of speed input `x` satisfies the assumption that `x` is in the range $[0, 400]$. Constant parameters are specified by invariants of the type `(= <symbol> <value>)`.

The sections `inputsymbols` and `outputsymbols` in the symbol file describe the conditions in the software control flow graph that are related to input variables and output variables, respectively. The control flow of the IuT is determined by the conditions over the input alphabet, which is expressed by if-conditions and loop-conditions. Each condition over input variables must be extracted from the code and expressed in symbolic prefix-notation, to allow for automated generation of the symbolic input and output alphabets, as described in Section 3. Note that conditions over internal state variables are not extracted, since

[§] <https://gitlab.informatik.uni-bremen.de/projects/29053>

[¶] <https://bitbucket.org/JanPeleska/libfsmtest/>

[#] <https://fsmtestcloud.informatik.uni-bremen.de>

^{||} <https://smtlib.github.io/SMTLIB/SMTLIBTutorial.pdf>

```

1  identifiers
2  input  real  x
3  input  real iaux1
4  input  bool iaux2
5  output real  y
6  input  real  vmax
7  input  real  c
8  input  real  delta
9
10 invariants
11 (and (>= x 0) (<= x 400))
12 (and (>= iaux1 0.9) (<= iaux1 1.1))
13 (= vmax 200.0)
14 (= c 100.0)
15 (= delta 10.0)
16
17 inputsymbols
18 (< x vmax)
19 (> x vmax)
20 (< x (- vmax delta))
21 (= iaux2 true)
22 (= iaux2 false)
23 (and (>= iaux1 0.9) (<= iaux1 1.1))
24
25 outputsymbols
26 (= y 0)
27 (= y (/ x c))
28 (= y iaux1)
29
30 #states
31 3
32

```

Listing 5 Symbol file for `IuTBrake()`.

these are identified automatically during the learning process and encoded as enumerated states and associated transitions. Recall from Section 2 that only the positive form of the conditions from the control flow graph are needed, as they appear in if and loop conditions in the code. Their negations are created internally by the tool, when calculating the symbolic input alphabet. Output expressions corresponding to all assignments to output variables in the code are listed in the `outputsymbols` section of the symbol file.

Furthermore, the `#states` section of the symbol file contains an upper bound for the number of distinguishable internal control states of the IuT. This is required to ensure completeness of the test suites used during the learning process (see Section 4.1.2). Note that the whole creation of the symbol file can be partially automated by means of static analyzers, but this topic is outside the scope of this article.

Finally, the LTL properties from Example 2 are specified in prefix notation, each in a separate property file. The compilation of the IuT must be performed by `clang` with fuzzing flags enabled `-fsanitize=fuzzer`. The test verdicts and statistics are shown in Table 3.

The test was executed in a Ubuntu 22.04 docker container[†] on our kubernetes cluster[‡] with an AMD EPYC 7702 CPU and maximum 256GB RAM, but 1 CPU core and 16GiB of RAM have been assigned to the docker container. The test results are shown in Table 3. All three tests were passed in under 5 seconds. For test of LTL formula Φ_1 , 22 input equivalence classes, for LTL formula Φ_2 , 20 input equivalence classes and Φ_3 , 12 input equivalence classes have been calculated by our tool. The maximum allowed fuzzing rounds were set to 5000, however, after less than 1000 steps, three distinguishable states were already found in all test executions. For all tests, the fuzzer seed was set to `-seed=1`.

As expected for such a small IuT, all properties were passed in fairly short time, as shown in Table 3. Unsurprisingly, 100% code coverage (decision coverage) was reached, since this is a necessary prerequisite for any complete software testing method, and the module does not contain unreachable code. It is interesting to note that a high code coverage is usually reached already while using the `llvm libfuzzer` during the initial fuzzing phase of the learning and verification process (see Section 7).

[†] <https://www.docker.com/>

[‡] <https://kubernetes.io/>

TABLE 3 The set of LTL properties checked on the `Brake()` implementation.

#	LTL formula	Description	Input Equivalence Classes	Verdict	Execution Time
Φ_1	$(y \leq 1.1)\mathbf{W}(x > v_{\max})$	<i>As long as the value of x does not exceed threshold v_{\max}, any braking intervention will apply a force that is less or equal to 1.1.</i>	22	PASS	4.88s
Φ_2	$\mathbf{G}(y \geq 1.9 \Rightarrow \mathbf{X}(y \geq 1.9 \vee x < v_{\max} - 10))$	<i>Whenever a brake force greater or equal than 1.9 is applied, this will also be the case in the next step, unless the actual speed is decreased below $v_{\max} - \text{delta}$.</i>	20	PASS	4.53s
Φ_3	$\mathbf{GF}(x < v_{\max} - \text{delta}) \Rightarrow \mathbf{GF}(y = 0)$	<i>If the speed always falls back below $v_{\max} - \text{delta}$, the brake force will always be reset to zero.</i>	12	PASS	4.19s

8.2 | Strongly Fair Scheduler

In this section, a strongly fair scheduler (SFS) representing an implementable version of the universally fair scheduler presented by Apt, de Boer, and Olderog [2], is tested. The SFS can be implemented as a task scheduler in an operating system to fairly select the next task to be executed. The SFS is a weight-based scheduler, where always a runnable task with a lowest weight gets scheduled. If a next task to schedule is found, the weight of the task to be scheduled is reset to a non-negative random integer, while the weights of the remaining runnable tasks are decremented. If no task is runnable, the idle task with id `NUM_PROCS` is scheduled. The SFS main function `fairSched()` shown in Listing 6 has function parameters `r[]` and `rnd`. The first parameter, `r[]`, is an array of Booleans indicating by `r[p] = true` whether some process with id $p \in \{0, \dots, \text{NUM_PROCS} - 1\}$ is runnable. The second parameter, `rnd`, stands for a random value in fixed range $\text{rnd} \in \{0, \dots, \text{MAX_RND}\}$ to be used as the new weight for the next scheduled task.

First, as shown in Listing 6, the first runnable task id with the lowest weight is selected by function `getId()` from the array `r[]`. Next, the weights of all runnable tasks are decremented by function `decrementWeights()`. Then the task to be scheduled gets the random weight `rnd`. Intuitively speaking, the chances of all runnable process that did *not* get the CPU are improved, since their weights will finally become negative, while the weights of the scheduled tasks are non-negative. Apt et al. [2] provide a mathematical proof for the scheduler’s *strong fairness property*: every task that is runnable infinitely often is scheduled infinitely often as well. We will verify this fairness property **R2** here, together with an additional safety property **R2**, by means of gray box checking.

R1. *If task p is never runnable, it will never be scheduled as next task y .*

R2. *If task p is runnable infinitely often, then it will also be scheduled infinitely often as the next task y .*

In LTL, these requirements are formalized by the formulas

$$\Phi_1 \equiv \mathbf{G}(\neg r[p]) \Rightarrow \mathbf{G}(y \neq p), \quad (13)$$

$$\Phi_2 \equiv \mathbf{GF}(r[p]) \Rightarrow \mathbf{GF}(y = p). \quad (14)$$

8.2.1 | Test Setup

For testing, different configurations are used. The first configuration runs with number of tasks configured `NUM_PROCS = 2`, and maximum random value `MAX_RND = 2` to test the trivial case. As a performance benchmark of our gray box checker, these values are increased in further test executions. Function parameters `r[]` and `rnd` are the inputs to the IuT and the return value `pid` of function `fairSched()` is the IuT output, respectively.

Exploring the internal state space during the learning phase is much more complex here in comparison to the `Brake()` example: The internal state is expressed by the combinations over the `weight[]` array, which stores the weights of each task. Note that the weight of the idle process in array element `weight[NUM_PROCS]` is never evaluated: it just exists so

```

1  static int weight[NUM_PROCS+1];
2
3  int getId(bool r[]) {
4      int pId = NUM_PROCS;
5      int minWeight = MAX_RND;
6      for ( int i = 0; i < NUM_PROCS; i++ ) {
7          if ( r[i] ) {
8              if ( weight[i] < minWeight ) {
9                  pId = i;
10                 minWeight = weight[i];
11             }
12         }
13     }
14     return pId;
15 }
16
17 void decrementWeights(bool r[]) {
18     for ( int i = 0; i < NUM_PROCS; i++ ) {
19         if ( r[i] ) weight[i]--;
20     }
21 }
22
23 int fairSched(bool r[], int rnd) {
24     int pId = getId(r);
25     decrementWeights(r);
26     weight[pId] = rnd;
27
28     return pId;
29 }
30

```

Listing 6 Implementation of the strongly fair scheduler.

that the assignment in line 26 of Listing 6 does not violate the array bounds if `pId = NUM_PROCS`, the id of the idle task. The maximal value of a weight is obviously `MAX_RND`. As proven by Apt et al. [2], the minimal weight of a task is $-(\text{NUM_PROCS} - 1) = 1 - \text{NUM_PROCS}$. Therefore, each weight can have $\text{MAX_RND} + \text{NUM_PROCS}$ different values. It has also been proven that at most one process at a time can have the lowest weight. Therefore, an upper bound of the number of distinguishable internal control states is

$$\xi = (\text{MAX_RND} + \text{NUM_PROCS}) \cdot (\text{MAX_RND} + \text{NUM_PROCS} - 1)^{\text{NUM_PROCS}-1}. \quad (15)$$

The symbol file, as shown in Listing 7, specifies test inputs in section `identifiers`. Currently, treating arrays as input is not possible, therefore one boolean input is used for each array element. For `rnd`, an input with the same name is specified with an invariant range restriction. The output of the LuT is the task identifier of the next task to schedule, denoted as `pid`. The section `inputsymbols` specifies all valid input combinations in positive form. This consists of all positive forms of `r0` and `r1`, as well as each possible value of `rnd` to force the solver to form a variation over `rnd`. Note that conditions over internal state variables are not extracted, since these are identified automatically during the learning process and encoded by combinations over the `weight[]` array. The `outputsymbols` section specifies the possible values for `pid`, where `pid = 0` represents scheduling of task 0 and `pid = 1` for scheduling task 1, respectively. The `pid = 2` is for the idle task. The number of estimated control states is 12, as calculated by Equation 15.

Both LTL formulas Φ_1 and Φ_2 were passed and successfully tested with the above mentioned configuration as shown in Table 4. All tests were executed in a Ubuntu 22.04 docker container[†] on a kubernetes cluster[‡], equipped with an AMD EPYC 7702 CPU and 256GiB RAM. For test execution, one CPU core and 16GiB of RAM have been assigned to the docker container. The execution succeeded in under 15 seconds, of course again with a 100% code coverage, as described in Table 4. The maximum of the fuzzing rounds allowed was set to 2000, and the fuzzer seed was set to `-seed=1`. The 12 distinguishable internal control states, as estimated beforehand, were found during learning, where 7 distinguishable states were found during fuzzing phase.

[†] <https://www.docker.com/>

[‡] <https://kubernetes.io/>

```

1  identifiers
2  input bool r0
3  input bool r1
4  input int rnd
5  output int pid
6
7  invariants
8  (and (>= rnd 0) (<= rnd 2))
9
10 inputsymbols
11 (= r0 true)
12 (= r1 true)
13 (= rnd 0)
14 (= rnd 1)
15 (= rnd 2)
16
17 outputsymbols
18 (= pid 0)
19 (= pid 1)
20 (= pid 2)
21
22 #states
23 12
24

```

Listing 7 Symbol file for the strongly fair scheduler test.

TABLE 4 The set of LTL properties checked on the strongly fair scheduler implementation.

#	LTL formula	Description	Input Equivalence Classes	Verdict	Execution Time
Φ_1	$\mathbf{G}(\neg r[p]) \Rightarrow \mathbf{G}(y \neq p)$	<i>If task p is never runnable, it will never be scheduled as next task y.</i>	12	PASS	10.42s
Φ_2	$\mathbf{GF}(r[p]) \Rightarrow \mathbf{GF}(y = p)$	<i>If task p is runnable infinitely often, then it will also be scheduled infinitely often as next task y.</i>	12	PASS	9.33s

For the benchmark, we measured time consumption and memory usage with different `MAX_PROCS` and `MAX_RND` configurations. The `runlim`[†] benchmark tool was used to measure memory usage and runtime. In Table 5, memory and time consumption with increasing amount of tasks `MAX_PROCS` during test of Φ_1 is displayed. In Table 6, memory usage and time consumption of testing Φ_1 relative to `MAX_RND` is shown. Again, all tests were executed in a Ubuntu 22.04 docker container on a kubernetes cluster with a extended configuration: the maximum allowed RAM is limited to 100GiB and the CPU is limited to one CPU core per docker container. For each further test run, the symbol file is adapted to the respective configuration by expanding the inputs `r0`, `r1` or adapting the invariant for `rnd`. Again, the `libfuzzer` seed configuration is set to `-seed=1` for each test run.

TABLE 5 Performance during testing Φ_1 on the `fairSched()` implementation relative to `MAX_PROCS`.

<code>MAX_PROCS</code>	<code>MAX_RND</code>	#Input equivalence classes	#distinguishable control states	#states found in fuzzing phase	#states found in learning phase	Runtime	Memory Usage
2	2	12	12	7	12	9.37s	441.1MB
3	2	24	80	14	80	5340.49s	57108.0MB
4	2	48	750	20	-	OOM	OOM
5	2	96	4375	21	-	OOM	OOM

As shown in Table 5 and Table 6, gray box checking is performed in acceptable time and with acceptable memory consumption, as long as the number of processes does not get too high. For 60 internal distinguishable control states, `MAX_PROCS = 3`, for example, the test was finished in less than three minutes and uses only 2708MB of RAM. With the use of only 2000 fuzzing

[†] <https://fmv.jku.at/runlim/>

TABLE 6 Performance during testing Φ_1 on the `fairSched()` implementation relative to `MAX_RND`.

MAX_PROCS	MAX_RND	#Input equivalence classes	#distinguishable control states	#states found in fuzzing phase	#states found in learning phase	Runtime	Memory Usage
2	2	12	12	7	12	9.64s	460.4 MB
2	3	16	20	8	20	14.75s	518.6 MB
2	4	20	30	10	30	76.53s	2290.1 MB
2	5	24	42	6	42	268.38s	7016.3 MB
2	6	28	56	6	56	1524.15s	28192.8 MB
2	7	32	72	6	72	3547.17s	53898.8 MB

FIGURE 5 Time consumption with increasing `MAX_RND`

runs, a considerable amount of distinguishable states were found. The number of calculated input equivalence classes increases relative to the number of `MAX_PROCS` and `MAX_RND` concerning internal distinguishable control states as expected. For testing `MAX_PROCS = 4`, `MAX_PROCS = 5` the test went out of memory (OOM) so that no data could be recorded.

Figure 4 shows the memory consumption in relation to growing `MAX_RND` and with static `MAX_PROCS = 2`. In addition to that, Figure 5 shows the runtime of test if `MAX_RND` is increased step by step. As a result of out-of-memory occurrences during the testing phase involving the expansion of `MAX_PROCS` and consequently limited data availability, only diagrams pertaining to the growing of `MAX_RND` are presented herein. As expected, the collected data show that both time and memory complexity grow exponentially in relation to `MAX_RND` and the number of input equivalence classes, as displayed in Figure 5 and Figure 4. The runtime of the test grows a bit faster than the memory consumption during rising complexity.

Since the model learning with the $L^\#$ algorithm consumes most of the running time and memory, the rising complexity can be attributed to the learning phase. Nevertheless, the results show, that even a module with 80 distinguishable states (see Table 5), can be verified in an acceptable amount of time and with acceptable memory consumption.

Despite the high number of distinguishable internal states, our implementation shows that with the use of `libfuzzer` and our implementation of the $L^\#$ learning algorithm, software module verification can be done in an acceptable time and memory frame.

8.2.2 | Error Injections

To demonstrate the soundness of the gray box checking tool, we injected errors in the strongly fair scheduler code from Listing 6. The first error was injected as shown in Listing 8. Compared to the original code shown in Listing 6, the faulty implementation of function `getId()` now selects a lowest-weight task from *all* available tasks and does not check whether it is runnable.

The altered software module does not need a new symbol file, since the guard conditions are still the same: though conditions `if(r[i])` have been removed in the faulty implementation of function `getId()`, these guards still appear in sub-function `decrementWeights()`. Also, the invariants and output assignments remain unchanged. However, there are less distinguishable internal control states: The output of function `getId()` depends solely on the conditions over the `weights[]` array. Regarding the `if` condition in Line 6 of Listing 8, for two tasks α and β , either the task with the lowest weight ω if $\omega_\alpha \neq \omega_\beta$, or the first task is selected if $\omega_\alpha = \omega_\beta$. Note that one task can have weight -1 , since the weight can be decremented by sub-function `decrementWeights()`.

Thus, as the weight of the selected task is replaced by input `rnd` and the weight of the non-selected task is decremented, the states of the `weight[]` array (0, 2) and (1, 2) now show the exact same behavior. More generally, states can be collapsed according to Formula 16, where pair $(\omega_\alpha, \omega_\beta)$ is the state of weights of tasks α, β .

$$(\omega_\alpha, \omega_\beta) \sim (\omega'_\alpha, \omega'_\beta) \equiv ((\omega_\beta = \omega'_\beta \wedge \omega_\alpha \leq \omega_\beta \wedge \omega'_\alpha \leq \omega_\beta) \vee (\omega_\alpha = \omega'_\alpha \wedge \omega_\beta < \omega_\alpha \wedge \omega'_\beta < \omega_\alpha) \vee (\omega_\alpha = \omega'_\alpha \wedge \omega_\beta = \omega'_\beta)) \quad (16)$$

Example 6. With $\omega_\alpha, \omega_\beta \in \{-1, \dots, \text{MAX_RND}\}$, where $\text{MAX_RND} = 2$, the number of distinguishable internal control states is 7. \square

```

1  int getId(int r[]) {
2      int pId = NUM_PROCS;
3      int minWeight = MAX_RND;
4
5      for ( int i = 0; i < NUM_PROCS; i++ ) {
6          if ( weight[i] < minWeight ) {
7              pId = i;
8              minWeight = weight[i];
9          }
10     }
11     return pId;
12 }
13

```

Listing 8 First error injected into `getId()` of the SFS.

As shown in Table 7 the first test in the first row, the property Φ_1 is violated by the faulty implementation of the SFS, as expected: the scheduler now assigns the CPU also to tasks that are not runnable. The second condition Φ_2 still holds: tasks that are runnable infinitely often are still scheduled again and again, it's just that tasks that are not runnable are also erroneously scheduled in between.

TABLE 7 Performance of verifying the faulty and the correct version of the SFS implementation – first error injection.

# Test	Property	faulty SFS		correct SFS	
		(time, verdict)	distinguishable control states	(time, verdict)	distinguishable control states
1	$\Phi_1 \equiv \mathbf{G}(\neg r[p]) \Rightarrow \mathbf{G}(y \neq p)$	(9.70s, FAIL)	7	(11.98s, PASS)	12
2	$\Phi_2 \equiv \mathbf{GF}(r[p]) \Rightarrow \mathbf{GF}(y = p)$	(10.55s, PASS)	7	(10.73s, PASS)	12

A second error injection has been performed as shown in Listing 9. A faulty return value in function `getId()` always returns the id `NUM_PROCS` of the idle task. Regarding this behavior, the output symbols of the symbol file must be updated: the symbol file shown in Listing 7 is changed by removing output symbols (`= pid 0`) and (`= pid 1`), since these output assignments no longer occur in the code. Due to the reduced output behavior compared to the correct version, there are no longer any distinguishable states, meaning that the incorrect implementation only has only one internal control state. The gray box checking results are shown on Table 8.

TABLE 8 Performance of verifying the faulty and the correct version of the SFS implementation – second error injection.

# Test	Property	faulty SFS		correct SFS	
		(time, verdict)	distinguishable control states	(time, verdict)	distinguishable control states
1	$\Phi_1 \equiv \mathbf{G}(\neg r[p]) \Rightarrow \mathbf{G}(y \neq p)$	(6.58, PASS)	1	(11.98s, PASS)	12
2	$\Phi_2 \equiv \mathbf{GF}(r[p]) \Rightarrow \mathbf{GF}(y = p)$	(6.24s, FAIL)	1	(10.73s, PASS)	12

```

1  int getId(int r[]) {
2      int pId = NUM_PROCS;
3      int minWeight = MAX_RND;
4
5      for ( int i = 0; i < NUM_PROCS; i++ ) {
6          if ( r[i] ) {
7              if ( weight[i] < minWeight ) {
8                  pId = i;
9                  minWeight = weight[i];
10             }
11         }
12     }
13     return NUM_PROCS;
14 }
15

```

Listing 9 Second error injected into `getId()` of the strongly fair scheduler.

As shown in Table 7 and Table 8, finding a property violation is always faster than proving property satisfaction for the module with verdict PASS. This confirms the statement of Peled et al. [30] that the complexity of proving the entire module correctness is always higher than uncovering a property violation.

9 | RELATED WORK

Our definition of SFSMs is consistent with the definition of *symbolic input/output finite state machines (SIOFSM)* introduced by Petrenko [31], but slightly more general: SIOFSMs allow only assignments on output variables, while our definition admits general quantifier-free first-order expressions. This is useful for refining output expressions and for performing data abstraction.

Meng et al. [25] confirm that fuzz testing can be effective for testing software against properties specified in LTL. However, their approach does not provide any completeness guarantees: the tool LTL-FUZZER created by the authors is to be used as an effective bug finder.

Pferscher et al. [32] also combine model learning and fuzzing, but with the objective to check whether an implementation conforms to a reference model, while our focus here is on property-oriented testing. The fuzzer is not guided by the code coverage achieved, as in our approach, but by the coverage of a reference model. Since the latter has not been validated with respect to completeness and consistency, the testing process can only reveal discrepancies between reference model and implementation, but not result in a correctness proof.

The model learning aspect of black box checking has received much attention since Angluin’s seminal paper [1], and a comprehensive overview about improvements and alternative approaches to automata learning is given by Vaandrager et al. [36]. We could have made use of the LearnLib library [21] for the model learning part in our Algorithm 4 (see Section 7). However, we would not have used the W-Method or Wp-Method implemented there for equivalence testing and finding counter examples, since our own library `libfsmtest` provides methods like the H-Method that requires far less test effort in the average case. Moreover, the new data structure and associated algorithms for learning that has been proposed by Vaandrager et al. [36] is not yet available in LearnLib, and it seemed particularly attractive with respect to maintainability and performance to us.

An alternative to LearnLib is AALPY by Aichernig et al. [27]. While its Python implementation seems less attractive to us, due to the better performance of C++, AALPY uses a strategy for disproving conformance between preliminary model versions and an implementation that is an interesting alternative to our current implementation: AALPY tries to avoid the generation of unnecessary complete conformance test suites by combining random testing with the W-Method, expecting to find early discrepancies between a preliminary version of the model and the implementation by means of randomly selected test cases. In our approach, we prefer to focus the application of random testing in an initial phase using coverage guided fuzzing with the objective to find an initial candidate for machine B with as many states as possible. After that, we rely on conformance tests without randomization, but create the cases of the H-Method incrementally, which also avoids the creation of a full conformance test suite as long as B and \mathcal{S} do not conform.

Waga [38] presents a black box checking approach that is complementary to ours in several ways. (1) The main objective is bug finding for cyber-physical systems, while we focus on *complete* property checks for software modules. (2) Waga applies

signal temporal logic, while we apply LTL. (3) Waga does not use any means of abstractions comparable to the equivalence class abstractions we consider to be crucial for complete property checking. Summarizing, Waga’s approach performs well for the purpose of bug finding on system level, while the method advocated here provides complete checks on module level.

Meinke et al. [24, 23] have surveyed methods that combine learning and testing, together with various applications beyond module testing as discussed in the present work. They consider only black-box techniques, so that our proposed approach differs from the surveyed methods by incorporating fuzzing and static code analysis.

10 | CONCLUSIONS

In this article, a novel gray box module checking strategy based on machine learning by testing and property checking has been presented. This strategy is complete: given any LTL property φ and an implementation under test \mathcal{S} , it decides whether \mathcal{S} satisfies φ under the assumption that a representation of \mathcal{S} as a symbolic finite state machine contains at most m states and employs only guards from a set G and assignment expressions collected in a set E . The sets G and E are documented in a symbol file required for the configuration of the gray box checking procedure. As m , G , and E can be determined from static analysis of \mathcal{S} , the strategy effectively performs a proof whether \mathcal{S} satisfies φ . Both the underlying theory and the tool platform provided by the authors support arbitrary LTL formulas, that is, combinations of safety and liveness properties.

The strategy improves previous checking strategies based on learning [30] in several aspects. First, it performs input/output abstraction and hence allows checking of implementations with possibly infinite input and output domains. Next, it employs fuzzing in order to quickly reach distinguishable states in \mathcal{S} ; this speeds up subsequent learning process. Thereafter, it applies the efficient $L^\#$ learning algorithm [36] and reduces the number of required test cases for equivalence checks by using the H-Method [12]. Finally, throughout the algorithm, violations of safety properties observed in interactions with \mathcal{S} are efficiently detected using a monitor [4]. The efficacy of these optimizations has been demonstrated both in this article and in a previous publication [9] in experiments with modules performing control tasks of significant size and complexity.

For future work, we plan to improve the tool usability for software testing practitioners by providing an intuitive frontend for property specifications that are internally transformed into LTL. For this purpose, we can build on comprehensive previous work elaborated in other research communities [35, 28, 15]. Furthermore, we plan to develop an argument for the tool qualification [8, 16] of our implementation, since we believe that the tool platform has considerable potential for the verification of safety-critical embedded control software in cyber physical systems.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors made substantial contributions to the conception and design of this article. All authors have been involved in drafting the manuscript or revising it critically for important intellectual content. Wen-ling Huang, Jan Peleska, and Robert Sachtleben described the theoretical foundations in this article. All authors contributed to the optimizations described in Section 7. Niklas Krafczyk and Robert Sachtleben implemented the algorithms described in Section 7. Felix Brüning implemented the cloud support for executing software module tests according to the approach described here, deploying the algorithms on distributed cloud-based services. Felix Brüning compiled all relevant material for the practical evaluation of the test approach. Felix Brüning and Niklas Krafczyk performed the evaluation and described its results in Section 8. Mario Gleirscher and Jan Peleska have the main responsibility for the final approval of the version to be published. Jan Peleska is accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no potential conflict of interest.

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